

Book of Abstracts

Edited by
Martin Behnisch and Mathias Jehling
(Steering Committee)

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Critical Landscape Phenomena

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC1)

Rescaled World Cities Leave on Land a Footprint of Wealth

VIGNOLLES, Victor; LEMOY, Rémi; RIVET, Thibaud*

Urban expansion builds on rich and easily accessible arable land, which is a concern for agricultural production, in a context of global climate change. It also affects ecosystems, contributing to the biodiversity crisis, and human health, for instance through air pollution. Soil sealing is linked to an increased flood risk as well. Worldwide measures aim to alleviate the impacts of urban expansion and sprawl, in small and large cities. However, the link between urban extent and population size is still unclear, as the literature displays contradictory results on this matter.

In this work, we uncover a radial scaling law governing built-up land in 1800+ global urban areas, of more than 300,000 inhabitants each (gathering more than 30% of the world population in total). We use for this UN World Urbanization Prospects and Copernicus' GHSL built land data for the year 2020. We study these urban areas through a mix of radial (center-periphery) analysis and scaling laws, a method which we refer as radial scaling analysis. We observe that world cities have homothetic (or isometric) radial land use profiles, and that built-up footprint is proportional to total population. We obtain these results through two independent but coherent analyses. On the one hand, through a rescaling of radial built land profiles, which provides a nice data collapse. And on the other hand, through non-linear regression methods, which additionally show that the mathematical shape of these profiles is roughly exponential.

The spatial scaling law which we observe is important for the understanding and the definition of urban areas, to help build a science of cities using robust empirical stylized facts, and to make cities more sustainable. It implies that small and large urban areas have similar internal (radial) structures, and that built-up area per capita is constant across city sizes. This suggests that efforts to curb land take (for instance in the frame of no net land take NNLT objectives) are needed equally in large and small cities. These results also lead us to define a new scale-free indicator of urban built land per capita, which captures the remaining variations. At the national scale, we find that these variations are very strongly correlated to wealth, measured by gross domestic product per capita. This very strong link means that land take on the one side and economic activity (measured by gross domestic product) on the other side are quite fundamentally intertwined in our societies -- which is not very encouraging for NNLT objectives. This actually suggests a pick between economic development and sustainability.

Keywords: land use, urban scaling laws, radial analysis, built-up land, center-periphery gradient

Contact:

Lemoy, Rémi
University of Rouen Normandy
France

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC1)

Identifying Subcenters across cities of different size using the radial population scaling law

*TONG, Yajing**; *CARUSO, Geoffrey*

Global urbanization has led to the emergence of large metropolitan areas with increasingly complex spatial structures, further challenging their sustainability and planning. Unlike medium-sized and smaller cities, these urban regions tend to exhibit multiple urban centers of similar size or a nested set of subcenters. Despite growing interest, the identification of subcenters and their relative importance remains inconsistent due to conceptual ambiguities, diverse data sources, spatial scales, and methodological variations across cases. In particular, local density or single cut-off approaches do not account for the fact that subcenters are heterogeneous in size within cities, notably along the internal general accessibility gradient, and for the fact that the relative importance of a subcenter vary depending on the overall size of a city, i.e. across the hierarchy of cities.

This study proposes a comparable and globally applicable framework to identify urban subcenters based on population density input. We employ a radial (center-periphery) analysis combined with urban scaling to account for both internal and across cities heterogeneities. First, a baseline profile is established for each city by modeling its population (exponential) decline from the main center toward the periphery, after accounting for its total population size (i.e. radial distance and density rescaling). Second, rings are identified that exhibit unexpectedly high average population density compared to the rescaled baseline gradient. Third, spatial filtering and a gravity-based allocation procedure are applied within each of these rings to identify subcenters and describe their population importance. The framework is applied to a global dataset of cities and the output compared to standard cut-off or local filtering approaches.

Keywords: Radial analysis, urban structure, population density, scaling laws

Contact:

Tong, Yajing
university of luxembourg
Luxembourg

*Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC1)*

Tracking Global Urban Sprawl: A Population-Based Analysis from 1990 to 2020

BRENNER, Anna Katharina; KRÜGER, Tobias; BEHNISCH, Martin*

Urban sprawl has become a defining feature of global urbanization. In regions such as Europe, North America, India, and China, built-up areas have expanded more rapidly than population growth - more so than in other parts of the world. This suggests that the drivers of sprawl have already surpassed population growth as the leading factor in land expansion. Continued population and economic growth, especially in developing and emerging countries, indicate a trend toward low-density development. These developments pose a challenge to achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target 11.3, which seeks to ensure that land consumption does not exceed population growth. Urban sprawl is associated with various environmental and social issues and undermines the broader goal of SDG 11: the creation of inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities. Despite its importance, long-term knowledge about global sprawl patterns remains limited.

Urban sprawl is defined as the decentralization of housing, employment, and economic activity into suburban and rural areas, characterized by scattered development, low use-density, and high per capita land consumption. This includes detached housing, dispersed retail, and large-scale commercial structures. The "Weighted Urban Proliferation" (WUP) indicator - used by the European Environment Agency (EEA) and incorporated into Switzerland's environmental monitoring - offers a robust, spatially continuous method for quantifying sprawl over time.

This study applies the WUP metric using the GHSL Data Package 2023 to assess global urban sprawl from 1990 to 2020. The analysis uses a spatial resolution of 100 meters and is conducted in five-year intervals. The dataset combines harmonized satellite-derived data on built-up surfaces with grid-based population estimates derived from national censuses. The sample includes all urban agglomerations with over 300,000 inhabitants as of 2018, based on UN World Urbanization Prospects. The most represented countries are China, India, the United States, Russia, and Brazil.

A major contribution of this study is the inclusion of a population-based perspective on urban sprawl. In addition to tracking land use change, we estimate how the number of people living in highly sprawled areas has evolved over time. This approach highlights the human dimension of sprawl and allows for connections to key indicators such as energy use per capita, emissions, infrastructure costs, and access to services. Understanding population distribution within sprawled zones provides policymakers with actionable insights—supporting targeted interventions, improved service provision, and the promotion of more compact urban growth.

By combining high-resolution built-up area data with harmonized population grids, this approach generates globally comparable insights into the scale and nature of urban sprawl. While census-based datasets have inherent limitations, the method supports robust medium-scale analysis and is particularly valuable in data-scarce contexts. It can inform more effective urban planning and policy-making in response to ongoing and future urbanization challenges.

Keywords: global urbanization, urban sprawl, settlement development

Contact:

Krüger, Tobias

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC1)

Beyond Urban Centers: Sustainable Metrics Through Expanded Urban Clusters in Latin America

PANTOJA MARDONES, Carolina Paz; SARKAR, Somwrita*

Defining an 'urban boundary' is crucial for urban planning as it is used to measure population and urban extension for global sustainable initiatives, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). With one of the highest levels of urbanization, projected to reach 90% by 2050, with urban population contained in a few primary megacities, Latin America presents a critical case for accurately defining urban boundaries. Since data on built-up areas are more reliably and regularly available than population, built-up areas are used as an indirect measure of population footprints. We employed clustering methods on the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) surface built-up areas and population and identified contiguous built-up and population footprints for all cities across 19 countries of the region. We then compared these "new" city footprints against the UN defined Urban Centers. Then we focus on the 65 most populated cities of Latin America and compare our new city definition results against their administrative boundary and the UN Urban Centers definitions.

By contrasting these different urban boundaries, the study identifies values and rates of urban sprawl. Results show that administrative boundaries and UN definitions fail to reflect real urban population distributions and built footprint growth patterns. To address this a new extended urban boundary is proposed based on the contiguous clustering results over Degree of Urbanization (DEGURBA) definitions.

Finally we perform comparative rank size analysis for population distributions and built-up areas comparing these new, administrative area, and the UN Urban Centers definitions. We find that boundary definitions strongly affect calculations. In general, at the whole country level, the UN defined Urban Centers distributions had significantly lower Zipf exponents (-0.19 (Peru) to -0.84 (Brazil)). In contrast, with the new definitions, the exponent values are significantly higher, ranging from -0.88(Peru) to -1.17 (Brazil).

In land consumption ratios we found that countries have concentrated their populations in their Urban Centers, but their built-up areas have not followed the same trend. The urban centers have become denser, but the built-up areas have sprawled with low densities, bringing overall densities down.

Over 70% of the population is concentrated in a few Urban Centers and the built-up footprint accounts for only 35% of the total in these areas. Except for Mexico and Panama, land consumption more than doubles for every country when suburban areas and sprawl are included in the city definitions.

The research identifies two primary forms of suburban expansion: Compact Urban Cores: Characteristic of smaller Latin American countries, where fewer dominant Urban Centers are surrounded by sparsely populated suburbs, leading to marked density declines and higher land consumption rates. Polycentric Urban Structures: Seen primarily in Brazil and Mexico, these cities feature multiple densely populated hubs surrounded by relatively denser suburbs, resulting in less extreme density loss and more balanced land consumption ratios. This research highlights significant gaps between administratively and standard defined urban areas and actual population and built-up footprints, underscoring the limitations of static thresholds and administrative boundaries in capturing the complexities of evolving urbanization dynamics.

Keywords: urban growth, city boundaries, satellite imagery, remote sensing, digital image processing, densification, suburbanization, Global South, Latin America, Structures and dynamics of cities, defining city boundaries

Contact:

Pantoja Mardones, Carolina Paz
University of Sydney
Australia

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC2)

Towards an open ETL Framework to support studies on mountain land sharing

LARKEM, Mohamed Zine Eddine; DEVOGELE, Thomas; BUCHER, Bénédicte; PERALTA, Verónica*

Mountain natural areas are the stage for diverse wildlife and human usage that often conflict. In the past years, outdoor leisure communities have particularly grown, leading to ecological pressure on wildlife. Scientists use different types of data to understand these ecosystems and elaborate recommendations to achieve sustainable ecosystems where land is shared. They spend a lot of time engineering data properly before being able to produce new knowledge.

The IntForOut project reunites ecologists and geodata scientists to use data from various sources to study human impact on mountain ecosystems in Mont Blanc and investigate innovative uses of stakeholder-generated data. We present the data engineering challenges encountered by ecologists and potential solutions investigated in the project.

Challenges in discovering and integrating data relevant to alpine ecology studies

Scientists studying alpine ecology use many data: hikers tracks, camera trap data, animals GPS tracks, habitat data computed by protected areas authorities, land cover and land use data, weather data, points of interest. These are different types of sources, publicly mandated authorities products, volunteered geography, crowd sourced data, scientific studies or private sector. The data is served from different portals, sometimes through a visualization interface only. The expertise required to use raw data, like for example the explicit meaning of terms like "acquisition campaign", is not explicated online.

Two highly important criteria for these scientists are : 1) the temporality of data, i.e. when was the data acquired and what is the temporal validity of it (which can be seasonal), when is it updated, 2) the sensitivity of data and the conditions under which the results can be published. Both criteria are hard to evaluate on current portals.

The raw data must be transformed and integrated before analysis, for example computing the human frequentation for each segment of hiking trail, or human-wildlife coexistence places. This often necessitates database manipulation and can also require spatial analysis operations.

Scientists encounter the following categories of challenges while deriving consistent data for their analysis : various temporal and spatial granularities across datasets, incomplete data, outdated data and different update mechanisms. Approaches developed in IntForOut project to integrate this data to address these issues, we define a dedicated open ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) process that assists in discovering, cleaning, updating, linking and documenting the different data used by these scientists. It consists in :

- an IntForOut ontology that describe data –including underlying concepts- and integration methods,
- a unified data warehouse, that can be replicated by scientists,
- a metadata information infrastructure, where metadata is any data about the data at stakes: structured metadata, official documentation, project description, readme files, fragments in meetings minutes

The next set of challenges involves defining a user interface to access the ETL operations, a generic process for integrating new data, as well as establishing an automated metadata generation workflow to document both the data and the associated transformation procedures.

Keywords: data heterogeneity, wildlife data, land data, integration, metadata

Contact:

Bucher, Bénédicte

Université Gustave Eiffel, IGN-ENSG, LASTIG, France

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC2)

Analysing the impact of landscape factors on the spatial dispersal of the pathogen vector common housefly using an agent-based model

*EICHLER, Lisa**

Many pathogens are transmitted by vectors, as is the case with Malaria, Lyme disease and West Nile virus, for example. Vectors can include arthropods such as mosquitoes, ticks and fleas, but also flies. From a landscape epidemiological perspective, vector-borne diseases illustrate particularly clearly how the structure of the landscape can affect transmission pathways and consequently the likelihood of pathogens being transmitted via a vector.

The transmission path of vector-borne diseases consists of three components: the host animal (usually wild or farm animals); the vector with its spatial dispersal; and the receptor (such as humans). From a spatial perspective, short distances between hosts, receptors and vectors can lead to greater spatial overlap and hence increased spatial likelihood of transmission. The study focuses on vector dispersal and provides a conceptual classification of theories underlying animal dispersal behaviour and the spatial transmission risk of vector-borne diseases. It shows that the landscape's structure, particularly with regard to the availability and permeability of resources, can have a strong influence on the spread of the vector.

To analyse the extent to which landscape structure affects the transmission between host and receptor from a spatial perspective, an agent-based model for the common housefly (*Musca domestica*) as a vector for antimicrobial-resistant microorganisms is developed. To this end, the landscape surrounding of selected pig farms in Eastern Germany— potential sources of antimicrobial resistance — was empirically analysed in terms of its resource availability, permeability and dispersal potential for the fly. The focus was on the impact of various land cover types and landscape (linear) elements, such as hedges. For the agent-based model, the landscape within a three kilometres radius of the selected pig farms was modelled in terms of its structure and the availability of resources using various data sets (e.g. a land cover model, LiDAR data, and information on specific land uses). The results so far indicate, that the landscape structure with its arrangement of land cover and the presence of linear landscape elements has influences the spread of the common housefly.

Keywords: vector-borne diseases, landscape epidemiology, animal movement, *Musca domestica*, agent-based model

Contact:

Eichler, Lisa

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC2)

Human-Elephant Conflict in Sri Lanka: A Geo-AI and LUCIS-Based Integrated Land Use Planning Framework

*JAYASINGHE, Amila**; *DIWYANJALI, Gayesha*; *SANKALPA, Sandaruwan*; *KAVEESHA, Lahiru*; *ABENAYAKE, Chethika*; *DE SILVA, Chathura*

Human-wildlife conflict constitutes a critical challenge in biodiversity-rich yet densely populated regions, where rapid land-use change compromises both ecological integrity and human safety. In Sri Lanka, escalating encounters between humans and elephants reflect deeper spatial tensions rooted in habitat fragmentation, land-use competition, and policy misalignment. This study proposes an advanced geospatial decision-support framework that integrates Geographic Information Science (GIS), geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI), spatial negotiation, and cellular automata to model and mitigate land-use conflicts at the landscape scale. The research builds upon and enhances the Land Use Conflict Identification Strategy (LUCIS), introducing a multi-layered modeling approach that evaluates land suitability for three competing uses: wildlife conservation, agriculture, and human settlements. Suitability models are developed using ecological, topographic, climatic, and infrastructural variables, informed by stakeholder consultations and institutional priorities. Spatial overlay analysis on a 1 km² grid resolution revealed that 48.8% of documented human-elephant conflict incidents occur in areas concurrently suitable for agriculture and elephant habitats. A further 21.6% occur in zones where all three land uses intersect, signifying spatial hotspots of acute ecological vulnerability and socio-economic pressure.

Case-specific findings provide critical insights into conflict drivers. First, smallholder agricultural expansion into elephant corridors emerges as the dominant spatial pressure, fragmenting key migration routes. Second, settlement encroachment along forest edges contributes to over 30% of recent conflict incidents. Third, unbuffered infrastructure development intensifies landscape impermeability, obstructing animal movement. Fourth, current administrative boundaries are misaligned with ecological zones, complicating cross-jurisdictional coordination. The spatial model demonstrates that by reallocating land based on ecological and anthropocentric suitability, high-conflict zones can be reduced by 15%, while preserving over 70% of identified elephant migratory pathways.

The framework's core innovation lies in its conflict-sensitive land allocation process. A game-theoretic spatial negotiation model assigns dynamic weights to land-use priorities derived from stakeholder perspectives and biophysical constraints. This enables fine-tuned trade-offs between conservation and development, generating land-use zones that are not only functionally coherent but also socially and ecologically legitimate. Cellular automata are employed to simulate adjacency-based transitions and reduce patch-level fragmentation, thereby reinforcing spatial continuity and landscape permeability.

By incorporating a predictive, data-driven methodology, the framework addresses critical landscape phenomena including habitat fragmentation, biodiversity loss, impaired animal movement, and reduced ecosystem connectivity. The approach transcends conventional reactive measures by offering proactive spatial interventions that prioritize long-term sustainability and coexistence. The integration of AI-enhanced modeling, participatory zoning logic, and dynamic land simulation positions this study as a significant contribution to the discourse on spatial interactions, scaling, and ecological resilience in contested landscapes. In aligning with the ILUS 2025 sub-theme on Critical Landscape Phenomena, this research provides an innovative, transferable methodology for resolving land-use conflicts in biodiversity hotspots. It advances spatial planning practice by embedding ecological intelligence into land governance, and contributes to a broader understanding of how digital tools can mediate between development imperatives and conservation ethics in a rapidly transforming world.

Keywords: Human-Elephant Conflict; Integrated Land Use Planning; GeoAI; Biodiversity Conflict Zones

Contact:

Jayasinghe, Amila
University of Moratuwa
Sri Lanka

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC2)

Urban Refugia and Spontaneous Ecosystems: Assessing Biodiversity to Inform Planning Strategies

*JENIKOVA, Eva**

The contemporary landscape is undergoing rapid urbanisation and intensive human intervention, significantly affecting biodiversity and ecosystem stability. Several studies (e.g. Aronson et al. 2017; Beninde et al. 2015) suggest that biodiversity in urban green spaces can often exceed that of the surrounding open landscape, primarily due to the extensive agricultural use and homogenisation of rural areas. Urban environments can thus serve as important refugia for a variety of plant and animal species, including threatened taxa. The importance of newly emerging spontaneous semi-cultural ecosystems is highlighted (Kowarik et al. 2018, Bonthoux et al. 2024).

This research aims to compare the biodiversity of urban green spaces of similar size (approximately 1 ha) in various urban contexts in protected (stabilized) areas and those planned for development or conversion. The study focuses on spontaneously occurring plant species differences and socio-ecological value between these areas. Data are collected through habitat mapping, and species richness assessments, using standardised methodologies applicable in both urban contexts and surrounding landscapes.

The goal is to gain a deeper understanding of the role of urban green spaces in biodiversity conservation and to provide evidence to support their effective integration into spatial planning and landscape management. The results are expected to contribute to the identification of valuable sites and to inform strategies that promote ecological stability both within cities and in their surrounding regions.

Recent work highlights the importance of recognising and managing urban biodiversity as part of green infrastructure planning (Aronson et al. 2017; Ives et al. 2016; Niemelä et al. 2011, Kowarik et al. 2025). By comparing urban and peri-urban habitats, this study aims to contribute to the evidence base necessary to balance human needs and perceptions with the conservation of ecological processes.

Keywords: Urban green spaces, Biodiversity, Spontaneous ecosystems, Socio-ecological value, Spatial planning

Contact:

Jenikova, Eva
Czech Technical University Prague
Czech Republic

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC3)

Balancing Agro-economic Development, Biodiversity Preservation, and Climate Change Mitigation: A Spatial Multi-Objective Optimisation of Land-Use Change in Brazil by 2050

GÉRARD, Thomas M.R.*; VERSTEGEN, Judith A.; NORDER, Sietze J.; DEKKER, Stefan C.; VAN DER HILST,
Floor

Over the past fifty years, Brazil has experienced profound land-use changes, emerging as a global leader in agriculture. Extensive areas of natural land have been converted into pastures, croplands and forest plantations, alongside expansions in urban infrastructure and road networks. However, agricultural expansion has occurred in critical regions for biodiversity and carbon storage, many of which rank among the world's top priorities for preserving terrestrial biodiversity and mitigating climate change. Yet, these biodiversity- and carbon-rich areas remain under pressure from agricultural expansion, as these lands are also suitable for agricultural use. Addressing this conflict is essential to achieve both profitable and sustainable land use in Brazil.

In this aspiration, this research explores how Brazil can meet its agricultural demand by 2050 while minimising impacts on biodiversity and carbon stocks. It aims to propose a range of alternative land-use pathways to meet future land demand in Brazil, with a quantification of the associated trade-offs between agro-economic development, climate change mitigation, and biodiversity preservation.

To achieve this, the research develops a spatial multi-objective optimisation approach using the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) to optimise land-use changes in Brazil between 2020 and 2050. The optimisation is conducted with respect to three objectives: biodiversity preservation, climate change mitigation, and agro-economic development. The outcome is a set of equally optimal land use configurations where gains in one objective come at the expense of another. This set, known as the Pareto front, represents the trade-offs between the competing objectives and allows for the quantification of how much improvement in one goal costs in terms of another. Each optimal land use along the front reflects the most efficient way to allocate land use based on a specific prioritisation of objectives. Finally, to guide real-world implementation, the optimised solutions are compared with land-use scenarios projected under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSPs). This comparison helps identify where and how the policies associated with these scenarios would need to be adjusted to move toward more sustainable outcomes.

The findings highlight trade-offs between agro-economic development and the environmental objectives of climate mitigation and biodiversity conservation. However, these trade-offs vary significantly depending on the socio-economic trajectory and associated levels of agricultural demand. Concentrating agricultural expansion in areas with high productivity potential, while avoiding biodiversity- and carbon-rich areas, appears to minimise these trade-offs. The comparison with the SSP scenario demonstrates that there is room for improvement in all three objectives, without much rearrangement of existing agricultural land. Overall, this research provides spatially explicit insights into how future land-use can better align with climate, biodiversity, and economic goals.

Keywords: Land use change, agricultural expansion, deforestation, environmental impacts, GHG emissions, Carbon sequestration, Species Richness

Contact:

Gérard, Thomas
Utrecht University
The Netherlands

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC3)

Biodiversity in a Growing City: Key Insights from Berlin's Long-Term and Distribution Data – A Baseline to Inform National, EU and Global Policy Goals

KEINATH, Silvia; FIENITZ, Melina*

Urbanisation is one of the most significant human-induced changes to the environment. It creates novel ecosystems that are distinct in terms of biodiversity from those in non-urban areas. Berlin, the capital of Germany, is one of the largest cities in Europe and has experienced intensive urban growth since the late nineteenth century.

Numerous national, EU and international policies have set specific targets for cities to protect and enhance urban biodiversity. Prominent examples include the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, the EU Habitats Directive, the European Green Deal, the EU Nature Restoration Regulation, the Berlin Urban Nature Pact, and the Berlin Strategy for Biodiversity 2030+.

Our project aims to quantify and visualise changes in Berlin's biodiversity, and to analyse the distribution of threatened species, in order to inform the implementation of these urban biodiversity targets. We have identified and compiled long-term population and distribution data on species, applying internationally recognised methods for temporal and spatial analyses. Specifically, for the temporal dimension we used the Living Planet Index (LPI) methodology, developed by the Zoological Society of London (ZSL) and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF), to analyse population trends. For the spatial analysis, we employed the Key Biodiversity Area (KBA) framework, a global standard developed by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), and adapted it for local-scale usage to analyse spatial occurrence of threatened species. Our results indicate a population decline across different species. The identified KBAs are largely situated within already established protected areas, some are also found outside Berlin's protected area network. This highlights the need for well-coordinated management and planning decisions. The approaches we used provide robust insights into Berlin's biodiversity dynamics, facilitating targeted conservation strategies and urban planning decisions that align with overarching biodiversity goals.

Keywords: Key Biodiversity Areas, Living Planet Index, Urbanisation

Contact:

Keinath, Silvia
Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC3)

A biannual, open LULC monitor supporting nationally determined contribution implementation and Paris-aligned adaptation in the Black Sea region

*SCHULTZ, Michael**

We present first results of a modified and enhanced Ukrainian instance of osmlanduse.org, an open WebGIS that fuses OpenStreetMap semantics with satellite observations to generate 10-m land-use/land-cover (LULC) maps on a biannual cycle. OSM tags are harmonized to IPCC-consistent LULUCF classes; gaps are filled via supervised learning on Sentinel-2 reflectance and, where available, Sentinel-1 backscatter. Change detection across update windows yields activity data for afforestation/deforestation, cropland–grassland transitions, wetland dynamics, and urban expansion.

The monitor is explicitly designed to serve Ukraine’s Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) and the Paris Agreement’s Enhanced Transparency Framework. Products align with NDC sectoral coverage and IPCC 2006/2019 guidance: wall-to-wall LULUCF maps, oblast- and raion-level aggregates, and uncertainty ranges suitable for inventory tables. Combined with tiered emission factors, these activity data enable estimation of carbon sources and sinks and identification of priority zones for nature-based solutions. A policy-facing layer stack highlights Black Sea basin vulnerabilities (coastal wetlands, riparian buffers, forest edges, peatlands) and mitigation–adaptation co-benefits.

Keywords: land use; land cover; OpenStreetMap; Sentinel-1; Sentinel-2; Ukraine; LULUCF; NDC; carbon accounting; adaptation; WebGIS

Contact:

Schultz, Michael
Tübingen University
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Critical Landscape Phenomena (LC3)

Investigating Human-Wildlife Spatio-Temporal Interactions to Support Sustainable Outdoor Recreation

*DAWSON, John; PERALTA, Veronika; DEVOGELE, Thomas; OLTEANU-RAIMOND, Ana-Maria**

In recent years, outdoor recreation has gained growing popularity, with a notable rise in new group-based outdoor activities. These opportunities allow people to explore and engage with nature, contributing to the economic development of local communities and, more broadly, to tourism. However, this expansion of outdoor activities raises concerns about potential negative impacts on biodiversity conservation. Scientific ecologists have introduced the concept of the “landscape of fear” to describe how wildlife, such as chamois, may be disturbed by human presence, potentially leading to altered behavior or even loss of plant and animal diversity.

At the same time, outdoor practitioners increasingly record their routes using GNSS devices, with trajectories shared as open-source data on different websites. Similarly, ecologists studying the effects of human activity on wildlife collected GNSS trajectories representing animal movement by using GPS collars. These parallel datasets open new opportunities to study spatio-temporal interactions between humans and animals.

In this presentation we will first present an overview of our research on how to study these human-animal interactions and propose solutions for sustainable outdoor recreation. Our research focuses on analyzing both human and animal trajectories to identify hotspots and coldspots which are respectively areas of frequent and less frequent co-occurrence. These identified zones first enhance human movement trajectories with ecologic data (e.g., chamois presence from April to June), and then it enriches a mobility network itself through map-matching techniques and attribute transfer, contributing thus to a trajectory-road network loop. Once the loop is finalized, the goal is to propose an algorithm that is able to suggest resilient routes which are routes that avoid temporal hotspots of human-wildlife interaction offering alternative paths that are less crowded and more environmentally sustainable.

Second, we present the first results obtained in mountain areas located in the French Alps. While our study area is currently focused on mountain environments, we argue that this approach is transferable to urban contexts, where it can support the development of sustainable alternatives in densely visited touristic areas. For example, this tool can be used by urban planners and mobility services providers to redirect tourist flows to avoid overcrowded landmarks or ecologically fragile zones, thereby reducing pressure on urban green spaces while enhancing visitor experience.

This work is part of the IntForOut research project, which aims to develop methods and tools to better quantify human pressure from sports and recreational activities on alpine ecosystems and to suggest alternative solutions for sustainable tourism and mobility.

Keywords: Spatial Interactions, Animal Movement, GNSS trajectories, Human and Wildlife Tracking

Contact:

Dawson, John

Institut national de l'information géographique et forestière
Finland

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena

Critical Landscape Phenomena: Leibniz Workshop (LC4)

Anthropogenic and habitat driven decline in movement wide-ranging nomadic ungulate

*CHATTERJEE, Nilanjan**; *MUELLER, Thomas*; *DEJID, Nandinsetseg*

Anthropogenic barriers alter and disrupt animal movements and are extremely challenging obstacles for long-ranging ungulate species. Understanding these disruptions and mitigating adverse impacts on wildlife requires knowledge of species-specific habitat needs and behaviors. How different linear features such as roads, railways and fences affect ungulate behaviors may differ greatly in relation to the feature permeability and disturbance, which in turn may be shaped by differences in physical structure or human activity. In the South Gobi region of Mongolia linear infrastructure is expanding at an unprecedented rate, creating barriers for migratory wildlife. We assessed the interactions of 99 Mongolian wild-ass also known as Khulan (*Equus hemionus hemionus*) at different types of linear infrastructures (roads, railways) and anthropogenic presence (mines) in the South Gobi of Mongolia. We calculated the number of interactions between the khulan trajectories and linear features and further categorized them into different behavioral responses (normal vs altered). Using a generalized mixed-effects model, we analyzed the factors influencing infrastructure crossings, including traffic volume, infrastructure type, time of day, and proximity to linear features. Our results revealed significant behavioral changes in response to different linear infrastructures. Khulan took notably longer time to cross these features, with paved roads exhibiting the highest traffic volumes proving to be the least permeable. Moreover, these roads were typically crossed at night during periods of low traffic. Furthermore, frequency of altered movement behavior around linear infrastructure increased three- to fourfold over a ten-year period. Highly mobile species utilize resources across vast landscapes, and we found strong evidence that linear infrastructures are severely impacting khulan movement behaviors in the South Gobi. These altered behaviors, driven by barriers, likely reduce access to quality forage, ultimately jeopardizing fitness and survival. Our findings emphasize key infrastructure and landscape features that, if properly managed, could enhance landscape permeability. This research highlights that the various linear infrastructure being developed in the South Gobi is altering behavior and creating challenges for migratory species whose ability to move across the landscape is crucial to their survival. Mitigation measures of linear infrastructure must be initiated to preserve connectivity to ensure the survival of khulan and other species in the region.

Keywords: Animal behaviour, Habitat, Infrastructure, Movement

Contact:

Chatterjee, Nilanjan

Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Institute
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena

Critical Landscape Phenomena: Leibniz Workshop (LC4)

Optimising Urban Permeability for Animals Using AI and Empirical Connectivity Models

MERKENS, Lisa; MIMET, Anne; WEISSER, Wolfgang W.; EQUIHUA, Julián*

Urban expansion substantially contributes to global biodiversity loss. As a result, conservationists aim to reconcile biodiversity and urban development and increasingly intend to promote biodiversity within cities. Given the limited space in urban areas, improving ecological connectivity, thus enabling animal movement between remote green spaces, is a key strategy to support urban-dwelling species.

Urban connectivity models are now commonly used to understand animal movement, but translating these models into concrete spatial recommendations, such as where to establish new green spaces or how to shape them in new neighbourhoods, remains challenging. In this study, we present an approach that combines empirically derived connectivity models with reinforcement learning, an emerging field of artificial intelligence, to perform an optimisation. The aim of this optimisation is to identify the locations where greening would most effectively increase the permeability of urban environments for animal movement and hereby support animal establishment in cities.

Our connectivity model used observations of a frequently observed urban bird species, the common blackbird (*Turdus merula*), to estimate typical movement distances and species-specific landscape resistance. It then utilised these parameters to derive landscape graphs and calculate the Probability of Connectivity, a relative measure of the connectivity of the overall landscape. Our reinforcement learning framework calculated the Probability of Connectivity as a reward function, where a computational agent iteratively placed green patches within the study area, received feedback on the resulting connectivity, and adjusted its strategy accordingly. Our coupled models identified locations that would most effectively increase ecological connectivity if greened. We found that elongated stepping stones produced the greatest gains in connectivity. Moreover, we determined landscape configurations where small interventions could yield disproportionately high improvements in permeability. Overall, we demonstrated the strength of reinforcement learning to solve spatial optimisation problems in urban ecology and planning. By integrating empirically derived ecological connectivity models with AI-based optimisation, our approach offers a decision-support tool for enhancing biodiversity through targeted urban greening.

Keywords: ecological connectivity, AI, landscape resistance, animal movement, optimisation

Contact:

Merkens, Lisa

Technical University of Munich
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena

Critical Landscape Phenomena: Leibniz Workshop (LC4)

Settlement percolation: global calculation of Critical Distances

SCHORCHT, Martin; RYBSKI, Diego; BEHNISCH, Martin; MÜLLER, Thomas; XU, Wenjing; BEUMER, Larissa*

The investigation of the settlement structure and its connectivity can provide information about the influence of humanity on its environment. In the study presented here, we examined the percolation of built-up areas worldwide, which was carried out as part of the study "Landscape Criticality in the Anthropocene - Biodiversity, Renewables and Settlements (CriticalL)". Percolation describes the distance from which larger cluster structures arise and therefore provides information on how close settlement structures are to each other and how permeable they are. Findings on this are of interest not only for economic but also for ecological issues, e.g. how permeable larger settlement areas are for animals. We pursue two measurement approaches with which we can describe for different spatial units how the settlement structures are connected, the so-called critical distance, and how wide open spaces are. Several global datasets were created, which address different levels of spatial resolution. In addition to administrative spatial units, such as country borders and subnational levels, critical distances were also calculated for different grid widths (5 to 0.5 degrees). Furthermore, raster datasets were created in which moving window approaches with different radii were applied in order to be able to make statements at the smallest possible scale. At the raster level, we have also calculated the permeability for different directions (north to south, west to east), which is of particular interest for studies of animal pathways. Besides providing the data, an easy-to-use Docker tool (CriticalL Mapper) has also been developed so that the approaches presented here can be easily applied to custom data. Algorithms specially developed for huge cluster calculations were integrated, which basically run with PostgreSQL and PostGIS in a Python environment. With the help of parallelization techniques, even larger data sets can be processed with high performance.

Keywords: percolation, critical distance, settlement cluster, global

Contact:

Schorcht, Martin

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena

Critical Landscape Phenomena: Leibniz Workshop (LC4)

Landscape configuration, not just composition, shapes terrestrial mammalian movements

XU, Wenjing; TUCKER, Marlee; BEUMER, Larissa; BEHNISCH, Martin; BRENNER, Anna-Katharina; CHATTERJEE, Nilanjan; KRÜGER, Tobias; OOSTERHOFF, Hanna; RYBSKI, Diego; SCHORCHT, Martin; MÜLLER, Thomas*

Landscape ecology theory has long posited that landscape composition and landscape configuration underlie ecological processes such as animal movement. While clear global-scale evidence exists supporting the key role of landscape composition in mediating animal movement, the effects of landscape configuration remain poorly understood at a global scale. In this study, we utilized a newly developed global settlement percolation dataset to examine the effect of configurations of human settlements on terrestrial mammalian mobility in human-modified landscapes. The critical distances provided by the global settlement percolation dataset represents typical distances among settlement patches (or “porosity”) of the given landscape, and we expect higher settlement porosity translate to greater landscape permeability for animal movement. Using animal tracking data from 8,379 individuals from 66 species, we showed animals in less porous landscapes move one-third less than in more porous landscapes, and this effect is in addition to the amount of human impacts. This research provided clear supports to the classic landscape ecology theory at the global scale that landscape configuration and composition are both key determinants of animal movement.

Keywords: Animal movement, comparative study, landscape connectivity, data synthesis, percolation theory

Contact:

Xu, Wenjing

Senckenberg Biodiversity and Climate Research Centre
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Critical Landscape Phenomena: Leibniz Workshop (LC4)

Land consumption and loss of open space in 2050

HOYMANN, Jana; DUGAY, Sylvie; BEHNISCH, Martin; BLÄTGEN, Nadine; DOSCH, Fabian; FRANZ, Elisabeth; POGLITSCH, Hanna; KRÜGER, Tobias; BERNARDT, Florian; ULRICH, Philip; PLASSENBERG, Jan; GUTSCHE, Jens-Martin*

The aim of an ongoing project by the Federal Environment Agency is to forecast the loss of open space by 2030 and 2050. A three-step process is being used for this purpose. With the help of the QMORE_PR model, future developments in settlement and transport areas in Germany are being projected at the district level up to the year 2050. The model takes into account demand-related factors such as economic growth, demographic changes, and sectoral structural change. By integrating it into the INFORGE macroeconomic model, the effects of a wide variety of developments on land use can be estimated. In addition, it has been expanded to include a module for mapping the expansion of renewable energies. In a second step, the land requirements determined at the district level are modeled in a small-scale grid using the Land Use Scanner model. The small-scale localization allows for an intersection with municipal boundaries, protected areas, and other regional settings in the course of the final evaluation.

Keywords: land take, scenarios, land use change

Contact:

Blätgen, Nadine

BBSR - Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development
Germany

Digital Twins and Decision Making

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT1)

Cities in Near Real-Time: Mapping Urban Land Use from the Digital Footprints We Leave Behind

DABBANAVAR, Ravi Satyappa; BISWAS, Arindam*

Urban land use mapping is a key application in city planning, infrastructure construction, and efficient management of resources. The process, traditionally, has been based on precise field surveys and remote sensing, which, as useful as they have proven, sometimes require huge capital outlay, time, and effort. Satellite imagery has made some of the impediments easier to solve because it has allowed large-scale land cover and indirect anthropogenic feature mapping. Nonetheless, data from satellites mainly record physical characteristics and do not have the level of detail necessary to portray dynamic socioeconomic activities and human uses of urban places.

In response to this void, the utilization of Geospatial Big Data (GBD) offers a revolutionary prospect for increased urban land use mapping. Social media data with geotags, especially, holds unparalleled promise for extracting real-time, spatially-delineated understanding of human activity patterns, thus offering an enhanced spatiotemporal concept of land use processes. Several recent research works have put forward frameworks for utilizing such data using temporal and content analysis, showcasing its ability to augment traditional land use databases.

Drawing upon these developments, our study investigates the incorporation of geotagged social media metadata to enhance the accuracy and interpretability of urban land use maps. We particularly use an exhaustive list of land use categories and subcategories developed by the Atal Mission for Rejuvenation and Urban Transformation (AMRUT), prepared by the Government of India. In order to further improve the coverage and richness of our dataset, we also include the corresponding synonyms and substitute phrases for these land use categories.

We have utilized natural language processing (NLP) models to examine the text within social media posts and prepare a dataset. This data corpus was used to identify keywords and activity patterns that are characteristic of certain land use types. Our initial analyses identify significant spatial clusters that reflect different land use categories. Additionally, through combining topic modeling with Geographic Information System (GIS) methodologies, we effectively group these activity patterns, providing insight into the spatial distribution and temporal dynamics of urban land use.

Our results show that data from social media, when integrated with machine learning and GIS models, greatly improves the level of detail and contextual depth of urban land use maps. This method offers planners and policymakers a cost-saving, real-time, and participatory tool to observe and control urban spaces better.

Keywords: Land Use, Geospatial Big Data, Machine Learning, Spatiotemporal Analysis

Contact:

Dabbanavar, Ravi Satyappa
Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee
India

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT1)

A Digital Twin of the Building Stock of Great Britain

*EVANS, Stephen**; *STEADMAN, Philip*; *SHAMSI, Haris*; *HUMPHREY, Dominic*; *LIDDIARD, Rob*

This paper describes the National Building Database (NBD), a digital twin of the building stock of Great Britain (England, Wales and Scotland). All buildings are covered, both domestic and non-domestic. The NBD has just been delivered to the Department of Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ) of the British Government. The paper explains how the Database has been constructed; lists the purposes for which it will be used; and reveals new findings about the stock uncovered by the work.

The NBD has been produced using the 3DStock modelling method developed over the last twenty years at the Energy Institute, University College London. It is constructed on a digital map base. The three-dimensional envelopes of buildings are modelled from LiDAR (laser) measurements made by overflying aircraft. Floor areas come from taxation records or are inferred from the 3D envelopes. Other data are incorporated on materials of construction, building age, heating systems and energy efficiency measures installed. These come from commercial databases and Energy Performance Certificates. Conservation areas and buildings listed as of special historical interest are recorded. Actual annual electricity and gas consumption from meters are matched to premises and buildings.

The Department of Energy plans to use the NBD for research on energy use and carbon emissions, and to inform government strategy and policy in three areas: improvement of energy efficiency and reduction of costs; examination of practical approaches to low carbon retrofitting; and investigation of the potential for integrating low carbon and renewable energy technologies. The Department will make data available in anonymised form for other users. Because all buildings are located geographically on their sites, the NBD lends itself to analysis of district heating systems, shared heat pump loops, and the location of ground source heat pumps as well as building-based measures.

Production of the Database has allowed mapping of the spatial distribution of building uses, building forms, and densities of development. The paper will include a sample of maps. One major finding is the very great extent of mixed-use buildings, in which different non-domestic uses are found (e.g. offices above shops), or domestic combined with non-domestic (e.g. flats above shops). These have tended to escape attention in research and policy but present special problems for retrofit.

Keywords: Building stock model, Great Britain, energy use, NetZero

Contact:

Evans, Stephen
University College London
United Kingdom

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT1)

AI for Very High-Resolution Land Cover Mapping in Climate-Resilient Cities

KELLER, Sina; LEITLOFF, Jens; GABRIEL, Raoul; HINZ, Stefan*

Urban areas are increasingly affected by the impacts of climate change, including rising temperatures, more frequent extreme weather events, and altered precipitation patterns. Addressing these challenges requires precise, up-to-date land cover data to support effective spatial planning and climate adaptation strategies. This study presents a novel deep learning approach for fine-grained urban land cover classification, utilizing high-resolution aerial imagery, and provides planners with actionable insights into surface composition and vegetation structure.

Our method classifies urban surfaces into eleven semantically and environmentally relevant categories defined in a participative process: three vegetation height classes (low, medium, high), three levels of surface sealing (fully sealed, partially sealed, unsealed), three levels of rooftops (standard, green, with photovoltaic (PV)), open space PV, and water bodies. The classification leverages a convolutional neural network (CNN) based on the U-Net architecture, trained using 20 cm resolution RGBi (red, green, blue, infrared) imagery and normalized digital surface models. This combination enables highly detailed semantic segmentation of urban environments.

To address class imbalance in training data, common in urban datasets, we apply targeted data augmentation techniques, ensuring adequate representation of minority classes. In addition, we introduce a multi-scale training approach, where separate CNN models are trained at resolutions of 20 cm, 50 cm, and 100 cm. This enables the model to leverage the specific advantages of each resolution: higher spatial detail for small features, such as rooftops, and improved consistency for larger elements, like open vegetation or agricultural fields.

Each resolution is validated independently and is then employed as a decision filter in a late-fusion strategy that combines the multi-scale outputs into a single high-accuracy land cover map. The final segmentation achieves an overall accuracy of over 90% in diverse test areas within the Frankfurt on the Main metropolitan region (Hesse), demonstrating both robustness and generalizability.

This work showcases the potential of AI-powered geospatial analysis to advance climate-sensitive urban planning. The resulting high-resolution land cover maps support a range of applications, enabling public authorities to monitor the implementation and effectiveness of climate adaptation strategies. By capturing detailed heterogeneity in urban surface materials and vegetation structure, the approach allows planners to identify spatial vulnerabilities and target interventions, such as cooling corridors, greening strategies, or reflective surfaces, with unprecedented precision.

Ultimately, our research bridges the gap between cutting-edge remote sensing technologies and practical planning needs. It provides municipalities and regional authorities with a scalable, automated tool to support evidence-based, adaptive, and resilient spatial development strategies in the face of accelerating climate change.

Keywords: climate adaptation, spatial planning, convolutional neural network (CNN), 20 cm resolution RGBi

Contact:

Keller, Sina
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT1)

Mapping Urban Morphology with Artificial Intelligence: A Cross-Contextual Framework

*TÜRK GRIGOLETTO, Didem**

The growing availability of open-access geographic data and high-resolution satellite imagery, coupled with advances in machine learning, is transforming the field of urban morphology. These developments enable more scalable, quantitative, and data-informed approaches to analyzing urban form. However, conventional methods often fall short when applied to complex, large-scale, and heterogeneous spatial contexts. Addressing this gap, the present study proposes a hybrid workflow that integrates Earth Observation (EO) imagery, image segmentation with AI, and morphometric analysis. By leveraging machine learning techniques, the method enables the detection, classification, measurement, and comparison of urban block patterns across diverse morphological settings, offering a replicable framework for large-scale urban form analysis.

The proposed approach adapts a U-Net convolutional neural network for urban block segmentation, using PlanetScope 3-meter resolution imagery as input and OpenStreetMap (OSM) data to generate training masks. Initially trained on the city of Barcelona, the model is tested across five additional cities, Turin, Paris, Copenhagen, New York, and Beijing, each representing distinct morphological patterns of urban blocks. This cross-contextual application allows for evaluating the model's generalizability and adaptability. Following segmentation, the morphological characteristics of the detected urban blocks are analyzed using the Momepy library, enabling typological classification and quantitative comparison with manually curated reference data. To assess the robustness of the workflow, a four-step validation strategy is employed. First, form-based multi-scalar validation checks spatial consistency across macro, meso, and micro levels. Second, numerical-morphometric validation compares geometric properties of AI- and OSM-derived blocks using a range of morphometric indicators. Third, cluster comparison validation analyzes the structural similarity between datasets by clustering their extracted numerical features. Lastly, cross-case validation evaluates the workflow's performance across diverse urban contexts, highlighting its robustness and limitations in varying spatial settings.

The results show that the adapted U-Net model performs with high spatial accuracy in detecting urban blocks in cities characterized by regular structures and delivers acceptable outcomes in more complex or irregularly developed urban environments. Subsequent morphometric analysis confirms that the AI-generated blocks successfully reproduce key typological features. Clustering based on geometric attributes further indicates a strong alignment between the AI-derived outputs and those obtained from reference datasets. Cross-case findings highlight the method's ability to generalize across varied morphological settings while supporting scalable and transferable analysis, especially valuable for comparative urban studies in data-scarce regions.

By unifying image segmentation and morphological analysis into a single, replicable workflow, this study helps bridge the gap between geospatial AI and urban morphology. It advances the capacity to examine urban form objectively and systematically across diverse global contexts.

Keywords: Urban Morphology, Artificial Intelligence, Morphometrics, Urban blocks, Earth Observation

Contact:

Türk Grigoletto, Didem

Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL
Switzerland

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT2)

Urban Digital Twin Policies to Address Liveability Challenges in Mecca City, Saudi Arabia

ALSHARIF, Anas; SENGUPTA, Ulysses; TANTOUSH, Mahmud*

Urban Digital Twins (UDT) are increasingly positioned as transformative tools for urban planning, design, and management cities. Enabled by the Internet of Things (IoT), UDTs allow real-time monitoring and data-driven decision-making to support long-term strategic planning (Batty, 2018; Deng et al., 2021; Nochta et al., 2021). However, their integration into frameworks addressing liveability remains limited, with most implementations focusing on operational efficiency and infrastructure performance rather than social aspect (Yossef Ravid and Aharon-Gutman, 2022). Currently, only a small portion of the processes that influence how the social aspects of the city operate are abstracted by city digital twins (Batty, 2018). To bridge this gap, Digital twins should be built on purpose and toward a specific goal that be design and operated to extract trends of certain essential aspects of the city system that enhance liveability (Batty, 2019; Caldarelli et al., 2023). however, In Saudi Arabia, national efforts aim to establish digital twin platforms across five cities, these initiatives aim to support the nation's transformation efforts and shape the future of Saudi cities. including Mecca, while also planning to host over 30 million pilgrims annually by 2030 (CEDA, 2016). These overlapping ambitions raise critical concerns about Mecca's liveability particularly under conditions of extreme temporal fluctuation highlighting what Rittel and Webber (1973) describe as a "wicked problem".For this reason, the primary concentration of the study will be on whether the smart city/digital twins strategic policies effectively address the specific liveability concerns identified or if the initiatives prioritise different aspects of urban challenges within the city to ensure that digital twin initiatives align with the needs and aspirations of the residents of Mecca city. The study adopts a mixed-methods deductive research strategy, combining 450 household surveys using a two-stage selection process across 63 districts with semi-structured interviews involving 15 government officials' decision-making from various entities. The qualitative strand focuses on interpreting strategic policy pathways, while the quantitative component uses a five-point Likert scale (1–5) to capture residents' perceptions of liveability. Descriptive statistics are employed to summarise key variables and provide an overview of how different aspects of liveability such as access to services, safety, and amenities— are perceived across the city. Preliminary findings suggest that current policies primarily focus on managing seasonal crowding during Hajj, while long-term issues such as housing, mobility, and environmental quality receive limited attention. There is also a noticeable lack of coordination between national and local strategies, and a clear disconnect between digital twin initiatives and the everyday needs of residents. Policy analysis reveals fragmented governance, weak cross-scale integration, and minimal alignment between smart city /digital twin strategies and broader sustainability goals. Furthermore, liveability concerns are often overshadowed by economic and technological priorities. This study initially identifies theoretical and practical gaps in the integration of smart city and digital twin policies within liveability frameworks. It calls for more adaptive, people-centred approaches that prioritise experiences and aspirations of urban residents. If strategically reoriented, urban digital twins have the potential to become powerful tools to inclusive, resilient, and sustainable cities.

Keywords: Smart city, Digital twin, Urban planning, Liveability, sustainability

Contact:

Alsharif, Anas
Manchester School of Architecture
United Kingdom

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT2)

From Global Goals to Local Action: An LLM-Augmented Knowledge Graphs for SDG Indicator Computation

BENJIRA, Wissal; BUCHER, Bénédicte; ATIGUI, Faten; GRIM-YEFSAH, Malika; TRAVERS, Nicolas*

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) define a global framework to address social, environmental, and economic priorities through a standardized set of 232 indicators. These indicators are designed to guide policies, track progress, and inform decision-making at all levels of governance. However, while their definitions are globally agreed upon, their implementation often requires local adaptation and disaggregated insights especially in urban contexts where spatial inequalities are most visible.

To operationalize SDG indicators locally, stakeholders increasingly turn to open data, a rich and accessible resource covering demographics, mobility, environment, and infrastructure. Yet, open datasets are fragmented, heterogeneous in structure and semantics, and often lack metadata. This makes integration and computation difficult, especially when aligning real-world data with the formal definitions of SDG indicators. We present SDG-KG, a graph-based framework that enables query-driven, explainable, and reproducible computation of SDG indicators from open data. The system combines Large Language Models (LLMs) and a dual knowledge graph architecture to bridge the gap between global indicator semantics and fragmented local data.

SDG-KG integrates two graphs:

- (1) the SDG Graph, which encodes the structure and computation rules of each indicator (goals, targets, concepts, attributes); and
- (2) the Metadata Graph, which represents open datasets in terms of schema, spatial/temporal coverage, and quality metrics.

Users define queries over a given territory and time range. SDG-KG applies LLM-assisted schema alignment to map dataset attributes and values (e.g., "bus" → "low-capacity transport") to SDG concepts, even across languages or inconsistent formats. It uses a Trust Score Metric (TSM) to rank datasets based on alignment with query constraints and data quality. An execution plan is then generated, translated into Cypher and Python code, and run over the selected sources.

We evaluate SDG-KG on six countries and two indicators: 11.2.1 (access to public transport) and 11.6.2 (PM2.5 pollution). SDG-KG supports interactive exploration of results, provenance tracing, and adaptation of indicators to the urban scale. In Paris, for instance, we show that computed values for 11.2.1 capture accessibility improvements linked to new transport developments.

By combining open data, knowledge graphs, and large language models, SDG-KG contributes to the emergence of semantic digital twins for sustainability. It empowers planners, researchers, and local actors to compute interpretable and actionable indicators aligned with SDG standards.

In summary, SDG-KG makes global goals locally measurable through transparent and AI-assisted indicator computation based on open data.

Keywords: Knowledge Graphs, SDG Indicators, Open Data, Large Language Models, Urban Decision Support

Contact:

BENJIRA, Wissal

IGN

France

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT2)

LLM-based Knowledge Discovery across decentralized public Spatial Decision-making Support Systems

*ITOVA, Irena**; *HIBMA, Simone*; *VAN BEMMEL, Bas*; *BOUWMAN, Arno*; *TROOST, Stefan*; *PIETERSE, Nico*

In the Netherlands, the integrated Environment and Planning Act entered into effect in 2024. It is an all-in-one law on the physical environment providing both legal security and direct spatial planning. Local governments are required to submit and manage permit applications, notifications, and spatial planning information through the Environment and Planning Portal, to ensure compliance with the Act. In this way, they provide transparent access to rules and procedures for citizens and businesses. Furthermore, through the Portal, many governments publish their so-called Soft Plans. They are non-binding policy documents which express local governments' long-term visions and ambitions. They can be seen as consultation (i.e. participatory) tools which support a dialog between different initiators and governments, guiding future spatial development and planning decisions. Through these plans, parties can check whether new proposals fit within local strategic visions, area agendas or development frameworks.

The national spatial planning and decision-making process in the country is highly decentralized, involving multiple layers of government (i.e. national, provincial, municipal and waterboards) with complex regulations and coordination across local planning and environmental strategies. The Act strongly advocates for integration, through a policy track specifically dedicated to environmental visions, and local governments are expected to execute their own vision's assessment and alignment to the national and provincial plans. The local environmental policy is then implemented by local Uitvoeringsagenda's Klimaataadaptatie, which are specific plans for adapting of infrastructure, nature, agriculture and the built environment to climate risks.

This complexity sometimes challenges the integral alignment of local policies in a wider context. For example, whether nature preservation objectives will be achieved depends not only on strengthening nature policy itself, but other related policies, such as sustainable agriculture targets to reflect the "critical values for nature". With the increasing risks associated to the changing climate on public wellbeing and the environment happening sooner than expected, there is a pressing need for governmental efforts on adaptation of local living environments to be more efficient across administrative boundaries and sectors. Therefore, the need to create automated tool that could help connecting and coordinating local and regional strategies to better align across sectoral borders is increasing.

To evaluate the spatial implications of plans submitted under the abovementioned Act against some of the associated climate-related risks (e.g. health, water security, agriculture, drinking water availability etc.) defined by PBL The Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, a dedicated workflow has been developed to collect, integrate and analyse relevant qualitative data into spatially explicit model on climate risks and adaptation. Textual documents and geospatial data files under the integrated Act are gathered from the accompanying online platform using APIs. After processing, their content was further analysed using decentralized open-source Large Language model. The LLM by means of question-answer workflow, extracted, synthesized, and reasoned over larger volume of various spatial plans.

Through a use case, we show how unstructured or semi-structured data from non-binding future strategic visions, next to expert knowledge, could be used to synthesize complex multi-source information and produce insight for spatial scenario-driven exploration models.

Keywords: Spatial Digital Governance, Natural Language Processing, Geo-Semantic Integration, Digital Twins

Contact:

Itova, Irena
PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency
Netherlands, The

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT3)

Spatial microsimulation of energy demand for future energy planning in cities: Scotland case study

*ALVAREZ GALLO, Daniela**; *NETO BRADLEY, André*; *BENITEZ PAEZ, Fernando*; *DEMSAR, Urska*

Energy prices have become a central concern for European households, impacting living costs and public welfare. Ongoing global conflicts have contributed to the volatility of fuel markets, making energy unaffordable for thousands of families. In Scotland, for instance, fuel poverty has been on the rise since 2017, with current estimates indicating that approximately 34% of the population is living in poverty or extreme fuel poverty (Scottish Housing Condition Survey, 2022).

Qualitative research has introduced the concept of double energy vulnerability to describe the difficult and often enduring trade-offs many households face, such as choosing between heating their homes, preparing hot meals, or affording transportation (Martiskainen et al., 2021). Simultaneously, the UK's NetZero Agenda, a national strategy aiming to reduce greenhouse gas emissions to net zero by 2050, is placing a growing pressure on the domestic sector to transition towards cleaner energy sources through household-level retrofitting and energy efficiency improvements.

These retrofitting schemes report an under-delivery rate according to the Energy Demand Centre, partially due to the lack of information on demand and socioeconomic circumstances at the local level that will enable local councils to offer relevant programs for different types of households according to their context (Kasprowicz, V. et al, 2024). A refined representation of how energy use is spatially distributed in Scotland and its relationship with socioeconomic characteristics at the household level is needed to approach these upcoming challenges. Unfortunately, the granularity required to understand the energy distribution at this scale is usually non-existent or unavailable due to privacy issues.

The goal of this study is to develop a realistic spatial microsimulation of Scotland's population and its current energy consumption patterns using synthetic population to overcome the privacy restrictions, drawing on data from the Scottish House Condition Survey (2022), the Census (2022), and the Consumer Data Research Centre (2015). The study faces some key challenges, including: (1) integrating multi-scale, temporal data sources while addressing privacy and granularity constraints; (2) evaluating and selecting the most suitable method for synthetic population generation; and (3) identifying and recommending optimal validation methodology to ensure policy relevance of results.

Following the development of an energy consumption spatial model for Scotland, the generated synthetic population enables the creation of exploratory policy simulations to assess potential impacts on local policy frameworks. In this session, we will present the synthetic population tailored for energy use studies and preliminary insights on spatial disparities of energy consumption differences.

Keywords: Energy demand, synthetic population, social inequalities

Contact:

Alvarez Gallo, Daniela
University of St Andrews
United Kingdom

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT3)

EUBUCCO: Europe's most reliable building stock dataset

NACHTIGALL, Florian; MILOJEVIC-DUPONT, Nikola; WAGNER, Felix; KOPP, Mira; NAPIONTEK, Jakob;
CREUTZIG, Felix*

Sustainable management of building stocks requires precise and comprehensive mapping of buildings' locations, shapes, and usages. However, detailed datasets with sufficient spatial precision and essential attributes are rarely available beyond national scales. Existing continental or global building inventories often lack the necessary spatial detail and attribute completeness required for many policy-relevant applications, limiting comparative research and large-scale analyses.

Here, we present EUBUCCO v1.0, Europe's most precise, attribute-rich, and comprehensively validated 3D database of ~320 million individual buildings, characterized by complete coverage of building height and usage-type information. EUBUCCO v1.0 achieves high spatial precision and completeness by integrating governmental, volunteered, and satellite-derived data sources using a novel, machine learning-based conflation framework. First, this framework spatially aligns and matches building footprints using 87 shape characteristics and contextual indicators, achieving an unprecedented matching accuracy at the continental scale with an F1 score of 99.5%. Then, it systematically merges and validates building footprints and attributes across data sources. Lastly, missing height and usage type attributes are inferred through machine learning models, achieving state-of-the-art generalization performance, with a mean absolute error (MAE) of 1.3 meters for building height and an F1 score of 0.72 for usage type classification.

Our analysis further reveals that relying solely on governmental or OpenStreetMap (OSM) data leads to spatially incomplete and geographically biased inventories, emphasizing the need for integrating satellite-derived data alongside robust conflation methodologies. Additionally, we demonstrate that commonly used intersection-based matching approaches, without prior spatial alignment, omit approximately one-quarter of true building matches, causing duplicates, limiting attribute enrichment, and erroneously excluding numerous buildings. Compared to the earlier version (EUBUCCO v0.1), these methodological improvements yield a 59% increase in the number of buildings and a 6-33% increase in ground-truth building attributes. By enabling comparisons across multiple sources, we provide transparent assessments of data completeness and ML-based attribute inference, establishing EUBUCCO v1.0 as Europe's most reliable and comprehensively validated building stock dataset. It provides a robust foundation for low-carbon, climate-resilient urban planning and evidence-based management of Europe's building stock.

Keywords: conflation, matching, building height estimation, enrichment of building data, machine learning

Contact:

Nachtigall, Florian
Technical University of Berlin
Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT3)

Socio-Spatial Analysis of Inequality with SoRa-Service: A Geolinking Approach

RIECHE, Theodor; EHRHARDT, Denise; EICHHORN, Sebastian; JEHLING, Mathias; JUNG, Alexander; JÜNGER, Stefan; ZAPILKO, Benjamin; GOEBEL, Jan; SIKDER, Sujit Kumar; MEINEL, Gotthard*

The spatial analysis of survey data combines social and spatial sciences in an interdisciplinary way, which entails a number of technical and legal challenges. The original survey data with the residential addresses of the people surveyed are subject to strict data protection and are made available to researchers in specially secured so-called 'secure rooms' in research data centres (FDZ). Thus, a data protection-compliant process is required that enables analyses to be carried out on the basis of aggregated data (e.g. to be able to investigate correlations), but does not permit re-identification. Researchers' access to the secure rooms on site is limited in terms of space and time. Comprehensive GIS skills are often required for the analyses, and the preparation of geodata sets and linking logics can be time-consuming.

The 'Geolinking Service SoRa' was implemented to close this gap and support for instance interdisciplinary research on housing equity. Linking socio-demographic and socio-economic data from surveys with spatial characteristics, such as population density and accessibility can give highly valuable insights and help answering questions like: How liveable is the neighbourhood for people who are particularly old, single parents or low-income earners compared to other social groups? How many parks and green spaces are there in the neighbourhood? How dense is the neighbourhood? Do residents living in areas with good access to daily amenities report higher satisfaction with their living conditions?

As a new research data infrastructure, SoRa Geolinking service intends to operationalise and simplify the linking of survey data with geodata. A distributed and decentralised infrastructure with several components enables the linking of different research data centres. Users can integrate SoRa into their scripts via an R package and access ready-made linking methods and geodata sets. The on-site use of SoRa within a secure room allows the original addresses to be used, while outside in public mode a synthetic structure dataset can be used to test links in advance. SoRa follows the principles of open source and FAIR, and can be expanded to include additional FDZs with new surveys.

The presentation will analyse exploratory spatial patterns of housing equity in Germany. The analyses are primarily based on survey data from the DIW Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP) as well as geodata from the IOER Monitor and the Federal Agency of Cartography (BKG), and can also be used for different time periods. The functionalities of SoRa will be demonstrated and a live demo (using JupyterLab) will show the user perspective. Finally, a discussion of the results and the potential of SoRa for socio-spatial research will conclude the presentation.

Keywords: housing equity, geolinking, survey data, research data infrastructure, linking service

Contact:

Rieche, Theodor

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT4)

Semantic enrichment of AI-detected buildings using remote sensing and multi-source geospatial data

HERTRICH, Moritz; STILLER, Dorothee; HELLEKES, Jens; WURM, Michael; TAUBENBÖCK, Hannes*

Knowledge about the functional use and exact location of buildings is essential for a wide range of applications, including urban planning, natural hazard risk assessment, and mobility analysis. However, comprehensive, up-to-date, and large-scale building datasets that contain both precise geometry and information on building use remain scarce, even in data-rich countries like Germany. Existing data sources in Germany, such as the official cadastral data (LoD1 and LoD2), provide semantic information on building types, but they are often incomplete due to data gaps, inconsistencies across federal states, and outdated information. Similar problems exist in building data from OpenStreetMap (OSM): while offering crowd-sourced building types, both the data quality and completeness vary greatly by region. Consequently, parts of the built environment remain unmapped and lack functional labels, impeding data-driven urban analysis.

To address these limitations, this study presents a scalable workflow that combines AI-based remote sensing techniques with multi-source data fusion to infer building use types across an entire metropolitan region. High-resolution aerial imagery and digital surface models are used to detect building footprints using a deep learning model based on a fully convolutional encoder-decoder architecture. Aerial imagery is used for the building detection because of its large-scale and up to date coverage, and its high spatial resolution. The model is trained and evaluated on annotated data from North Rhine-Westphalia and Berlin and achieves a mean intersection-over-union of over 92% on validation data. By experimenting with different training data sampling strategies, the model generalization is improved, and the best-performing configuration is applied to the full area of Berlin to extract accurate and up-to-date building geometries. This approach enables a systematic quantification of missing buildings in both cadastral and OSM building datasets.

Since most building usage types are not discernable only based on aerial images, additional data are necessary to assign functional attributes to the detected buildings. These include both previously mentioned official cadastral data and multiple OpenStreetMap layers, such as buildings and land use polygons. The heterogeneous usage categories from both sources are harmonized and mapped onto four generalized functional classes: 'residential', 'commercial', 'work-related', and 'other'. These categories reflect the primary daily travel purposes observed in urban areas, making them well-suited for urban mobility modeling. Adjacent buildings are spatially aggregated into building complexes and proportional type shares are assigned based on areal relationships from the external building datasets. For building complexes with no matching semantic data, functional approximations are derived from land use information.

The resulting dataset provides proportional use shares across the four target categories for all buildings in the federal state of Berlin. This enables a nuanced representation of mixed-use as well as single-use structures. Beyond quantifying data gaps in existing building datasets, the study demonstrates how combining Earth observation data with volunteered and official sources can fill critical missing information on building location and use type. This approach offers a scalable solution for generating semantically enriched complete building inventories that reflect current urban conditions by bridging the gap between building geometry and semantic usage information.

Keywords: Building Extraction, Deep Learning, Remote Sensing, Semantic Enrichment

Contact:

Hertrich, Moritz

German Aerospace Center (DLR)

Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT4)

Pioneering Colouring Austria: A Scalable Urban Data Framework for the Digital Twin Era

HERZ, Simon; GANDHI, Shaily; KESKIN, Merve; CHASSIN, Thibaud*

To address complex challenges in urban sustainability, Austrian cities are increasingly relying on powerful digital solutions. However, the efficiency of these solutions is limited by the quality of the underlying urban infrastructure data, which is often fragmented, inaccessible, inaccurate, or outdated. This paper describes the implementation of the Colouring Cities Framework (CCF) in an Austrian context, laying the foundation for Colouring Austria, a national-scale initiative for building a standardized, extensible platform for building-level urban data. Originating from the Colouring Cities Research Program (CCRP) at The Alan Turing Institute, the CCF offers a modular framework for collecting, managing, and visualizing urban data using open-source technologies.

Using the city of Graz as a case study, we benchmarked the platform's deployment, data integration workflows, and thematic enrichment. The broader research scope investigates how Austria's urban data landscape can be integrated into a modern, flexible, and scalable digital solution, transferable to other local contexts such as the city of Linz and Salzburg, establishing a cohesive national approach to urban data infrastructure.

Following the CCRP documentation and standards, the platform was first deployed using a PostgreSQL database configured to store detailed building information. The database was then populated with national open geospatial and semantic data, including building geometry, height, use type, and other attributes. Additionally, to demonstrate the platform's extensibility, we developed a test case focused on classifying roof characteristics and assessing the presence and potential of rooftop photovoltaic (PV) systems. The analysis aimed to identify roof geometry, materials, and solar exposure using publicly available data retrieved from federal GIS data portals, including airborne laser scanning and high-resolution aerial imagery. Based on these inputs, geospatial processing and classification techniques were applied to assign attributes such as roof shape (e.g., flat, gabled, hipped), material (e.g., tiles, metal, green roofs), and PV suitability to individual buildings. This detailed information was integrated into the database and CCPR web interface.

This test case highlights the framework's capacity to support advanced spatial analysis workflows and integrate derived data within a centralized, queryable platform. All components of the deployment, including system configuration, data pipelines, and classification outputs, follow open standards, supporting reproducibility, interoperability, and transparency. The platform enables both experts and non-experts to explore urban data through an interactive, map-based interface.

By integrating high-resolution geospatial data with a flexible, open-source platform architecture, the project supports a more granular understanding of urban structures and spatial dynamics at the building level. This work contributes to the creation of a single source of truth for urban data, aligning with broader goals in sustainable urban development, data-driven decision-making, and digital twin applications. Importantly, the experience gained through this implementation offers valuable insights for enhancing deployment workflows, platform scalability, and data integration practices. The lessons learned from this study are actively shared with network partners to inform future iterations of the CCF and contribute to the continuous development of the CCRP.

Keywords: digital-twin, open data, colouring cities, photovoltaics

Contact:

Chassin, Thibaud
University of Graz
Austria

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT4)

Towards global estimations of the age of the built stock: The Global Human Settlement Age (GHS-AGE) dataset

UHL, Johannes H.; PESARESI, Martino; POLITIS, Panagiotis; FLORIO, Pietro; KEMPER, Thomas*

Detailed knowledge of the age of the building stock is crucial for a wide range of pressing issues related to energy efficiency, sustainable development, disaster risk, and vulnerability of buildings and their inhabitants. Recent advances in Earth observation data collection and processing have boosted the emergence of (quasi-)global building footprint datasets (e.g., Microsoft GlobalMLBuildingFootprints, Google Open Buildings, Overture Maps buildings, GlobalBuildingMap), complementing volunteered geographic information such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) or the OSM-derived OpenBuildingMap. However, while geometric information on buildings is abundant, thematic microdata on building age or function are often limited or entirely unavailable. Global or continent-level data harmonization and curation efforts such as OpenBuildingMap or EUBUCCO partially provide building age estimates using authoritative data (e.g., cadastral data sources). Model-based inferential estimates, and country- or city-level crowdsourced and community-based efforts (e.g., the “Colouring Britain” project) effectively fill data gaps at country- or local scales. However, the potential of historical Earth observation data (e.g. from the Landsat archive) for explicit modelling of the age of building stocks and for enriching building footprint data has largely been unexplored.

Hence, we present and evaluate GHS-AGE, a global, free and open gridded dataset modelling the age of the built stock. GHS-AGE has been derived from global, multitemporal gridded estimates of built-up surface from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL), measuring subpixel built-up surface area on a continuous scale at 100m spatial resolution, in 5-year intervals from 1975 to 2020. From this multi-temporal global gridded data stack, we identify the year in which 50% of the contemporary built-up surface area was exceeded for the first time. This year represents, in the absence of further information, our best guess of the median building construction year per 100m grid cell. Mapping this year (or epoch) to each grid cell reveals not only striking pictures of urbanization and settlement expansion, but represents the first, global, statistically formalized estimate of the construction epoch of the built stock.

We compare these gridded estimates to authoritative (i.e., census, cadastral, tax assessment) data, as well as real-estate related data sources reporting on building construction years and find encouraging levels of agreement across different countries and continents. GHS-AGE complements existing, global gridded datasets mapping the evolution of built-up surface area (e.g., GHSL), settlement footprints (e.g., World Settlement Footprint Evolution), or impervious surfaces (e.g., GISA) by providing a well-defined, statistically founded semantic, estimating the median construction year of the built stock, consistently enumerated across the globe. GHS-AGE is provided as a global, gridded dataset at 100m and 1km resolution and enables large-scale raster-based analyses of the built stock, facilitating the integration with other thematic variables from the GHSL such as population counts, building height, functional (i.e., residential / non-residential) or settlement classifications, enumerated in the same grid.

While being of gridded nature, GHS-AGE constitutes also an important input to the Global Human Settlement Open Building Attribute Table (GHS-OBAT), a recent data integration effort to enrich global building footprint datasets like the Overture Maps buildings with remote-sensing derived attributes in a flexible and extendable framework.

Keywords: Global Human Settlement Layer, building construction year, building stock, building microdata, building footprint data enrichment

Contact:

Uhl, Johannes
European Commission, Italy

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Digital Twins and Decision Making (DT4)

Integrating OpenStreetMap and Satellite Data for Automated Landscape Change Detection: A Machine Learning Approach to Crowdsourced Land Use Monitoring

KHAN, Mohammed Rizwan; HERFORT, Benjamin*

Urban landscapes undergo continuous transformation, yet traditional monitoring systems, e.g. based on topographic maps produced by public administration, often lack the temporal granularity and semantic richness needed for comprehensive change detection. This study explores a novel approach that integrates crowdsourced OpenStreetMap (OSM) data with satellite imagery to enhance automated landscape monitoring capabilities. Building for the LaVerDi (Landschaftveränderungsdienst) operational service framework provided by Bundesamt für Kartographie und Geodäsie (BKG), the aim is to develop a machine learning pipeline that leverages the complementary strengths of both data sources for improved land use/land cover (LULC) change detection.

Our methodology begins with a quality assessment of OSM land use data in the study areas using the `ohsome-quality-api`, ensuring a reliable foundation for subsequent analysis. For efficient and scalable temporal analysis, we utilize `ohsome-planet` to access OSM data in Parquet format, significantly accelerating the processing of large-scale, time-series OSM datasets. We address the temporal offset between real-world changes and their representation in OSM by implementing a one year lag analysis between satellite observations and OSM updates. Using heterogeneous test sites in Germany, we generate OSM-derived land use rasters mapped to standardized classification schemes (Dynamic World) and compare them with multi-temporal satellite data through confusion matrix analysis. The approach uses high-resolution Planet RGB data to validate detected changes.

Looking ahead, we plan to develop machine learning models that can recognize patterns of valid change in OSM data by learning from historical satellite-OSM alignment patterns. The envisioned system would help distinguish between meaningful landscape transformations and mapping artifacts, and could automatically trigger validation workflows when significant changes are detected. Such a model would aim to validate OSM-detected changes against satellite evidence and determine when new LULC maps should be published, creating a more responsive monitoring system that combines the semantic detail of crowdsourced data with the objectivity of satellite observations.

Preliminary results demonstrate that OSM data can effectively capture land use dynamics, particularly for anthropogenic changes, while satellite data provides crucial validation for change authenticity. This integrated approach holds great promise for supporting sustainable urban development by providing more timely and precise landscape insights. This research contributes to advancing AI-based spatial data analysis, offering a scalable way to monitor landscapes by combining detailed crowdsourced information with objective satellite observations.

Keywords: OpenStreetMap, satellite imagery, machine learning, land use change detection, crowdsourcing, landscape monitoring

Contact:

Khan, Mohammed Rizwan
HeiGIT gGmbH
Germany

Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North

*Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN1)*

Mapping the Urban Fabric-Based Planning hotspots for transition to Netzero carbon Cities: A GeoNLP Approach

DAS, Sukanto; SIKDER, Sujit Kumar*

Cities are at the frontiers of convergence research, facing the dual challenge of supporting urban wellbeing of residents while reducing carbon emissions. This study aims to identify urban fabrics suitable for implementing net-zero carbon city planning strategies. Three fabric types are included—walking-oriented, transit-oriented, and car-dependent—defined according to the theory of urban fabrics. A reproducible geospatial workflow has been conceptualized, leveraging the best available open data sources, including functional Points of Interest (POIs), building footprints, and road networks. The methodology has been piloted in the case study city of Dresden, with potential applicability to global urban contexts. To classify land-use activities, a natural language processing (NLP) algorithm (e.g., Doc2Vec) is used for getting POIs vector embedding which helps to cluster the semantic patterns. Each cluster is annotated later by urban fabric type which receives scores at the grid-cell level by analyzing thematic relationships among POIs, building density characteristics, and road network configuration. Sensitivity analysis of grid sizes—200, 500, and 1000 m²—was conducted to investigate sensitivity of spatial resolution. The resulting dataset can be combined with high-quality local urban data to generate actionable spatial insights and identify intervention hotspots. These support context-specific planning tools, such as walkability improvements, public transport enhancement, and localized deployment of public e-charging infrastructure. By blending urban structure, land use, and infrastructure, this GeoNLP-based approach enables place-based comparisons and assessments that contribute to climate action—toward more livable, low-carbon cities.

Keywords: Netzero city, Urban fabrics, GeoNLP, Land use

Contact:

Sikder, Sujit Kumar

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

*Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN1)*

Digital Data As a Tool for Managing Urban Expansion – The Case of the City-Regional Observatory in Gujarat, India

*BANDYOPADHYAY, Saswat**

Unplanned urban expansion poses significant challenges for rapidly growing regions in the Global South, where weak planning systems and fragmented governance structures affects the sustainable city development. This paper demonstrates how digital data infrastructures can shift urban management from reactive regulation to proactive territorial governance, using the City Regional Development Observatory (CRDO) in Gujarat, as an empirical case. The CRDO integrates multi-source geospatial intelligence, such as high-resolution satellite imagery, land use data, infrastructure networks, and urban growth indicators, into a single and unified spatial decision platform.

Unlike the traditional land-use planning, the observatory enables continuous surveillance of peripheral development, early identification of the areas where land is being developed illegally, and clear understanding of how peri-urban areas are changing over time. The observatory supports institutional coordination between Urban Local Bodies, Development authorities, and various state agencies, providing evidence-based decision making, infrastructure alignment and environmental risk mitigation. The study reveals that data-driven planning not only improves spatial transparency, but also reconfigures institutional power, reducing discretionary decision making and enhance the regulatory accountability. However, it also faces challenges such as standardised data, limited technical skills, and resistance to data sharing. This paper argue that digital observatories represent a paradigm shift in governing city-regional expansion in Global South, embedding predictive spatial intelligence into planning systems and offering a replicable model for managing urban transitions.

Keywords: Digital planning, City observatory, Urban expansion, Geospatial data, City-region governance

Contact:

Bandyopadhyay, Saswata
CEPT University
India

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN1)

Combining Graph Neural Networks and Random Forests method to Predict Heat Hotspots in Ahmedabad

SHINDE, Chintan; GANDHI, Shaily; ROY, Samudra; ASODARIYA, Gargi; HODAWDEKAR, Riya; SHAH, Rachana; HIRANI, Siraz; BRAHMBHATT, Bijal*

Rapid urbanization and climate change are intensifying urban heat islands (UHI), with highly variable impacts across land-use types. Conventional heat studies often rely on land surface temperature (LST) or land use/land cover (LULC) data to extrapolate limited air temperature measurements. However, LST alone does not effectively capture the impact of land use on air temperature and LULC lacks sufficient granularity. There is a research in the existing models which provide static snapshots rather than actionable simulations to guide urban heat mitigation. This study presents a hybrid modeling framework that integrates Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) and machine learning methods, particularly Random Forests, to predict spatial-temporal variations in urban air temperature. In Ahmedabad, traverse-based heat mapping was conducted across 17 routes representing 13 land-use typologies, selected through an Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). GNNs trained on LST and LULC achieved high predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.94$). A Random Forest model, using predictors such as NDVI, NDBI, LST, and local vegetation density, further quantified the impacts of land-use change scenarios ($R^2 = 0.64$). Simulations showed that converting 183 km² of barren and sparse vegetation to dense vegetation reduced average air temperature by 0.16 °C, whereas expanding impervious surfaces increased it by 1.63 °C. The results reveal that applying GNN on a combination of LST and LULC generates a more realistic Air Temperature layer that can be used to aid policymaking. Secondly, from the Random Forest prediction model, it becomes clear that regulating the growth of impervious areas within in a city may have a larger impact on than solely growing trees. A combination of these two models, therefore, provides information about heat hotspots in a more effective way for urban policy.

Keywords: Random Forest, Land Use Land Cover, Urban Heat Islands

Contact:

Gandhi, Shaily

Interdisciplinary Transformation University Austria
Austria

*Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN2)*

Investigating Urban Thermal Dynamics in the Global South: A Spatiotemporal Remote Sensing Analysis

MOHIUDDIN, Gulam; MUND, Jan-Peter*

Rapid land-use transformations in emerging urban regions are increasingly challenging environmental sustainability and climate resilience, particularly in the Global South. This study presents a remote sensing-based assessment of the spatiotemporal dynamics of land surface temperature (LST) in response to land use and land cover (LULC) changes in Phnom Penh, a city in the Global South undergoing intense urbanisation. Using a semi-automatic workflow implemented in Google Earth Engine, we analysed over 425 Landsat scenes (2000–2021) and spectral indices (NDVI, MNDWI, IBI) to capture long-term seasonal patterns, extreme heat events, and correlations between LST and land cover characteristics.

The findings reveal a clear upward trend in LST associated with the conversion of vegetated and peri-urban agricultural land to impervious built-up surfaces. Site-specific analysis highlights substantial spatial and seasonal variability, including localised urban heat amplification in newly developed zones. Correlation analysis confirms a strong relationship between increased built-up indices and elevated LST, while vegetated and water-covered areas consistently moderated thermal extremes.

By offering a replicable and computationally efficient approach to monitoring urban thermal dynamics, this study supports evidence-based spatial planning and land governance. It provides actionable insights for integrating climate-sensitive design into urban development strategies, particularly in fast-transforming cities of the Global South.

Keywords: evidence-based spatial governance, climate-resilient urban development, thermal dynamics

Contact:

Mohiuddin, Gulam

Hochschule für nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde (HNEE)

Germany

*Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN2)*

Surveying the Past, Shaping the Future: Fifty Years of Urban Transformation in Ankara

SAHINKAYA, Cemre; ALTROCK, Uwe; SCHAFFERT, Markus; PAYNE, Geoffrey*

As in many countries across the Global South, the phenomenon of rapid urbanisation has significantly influenced the trajectory of urban development in the capital of Turkey, Ankara. Starting in the 1970s, the city witnessed a period of intense urban growth, primarily driven by large-scale internal migration from rural areas and the widespread emergence of informal housing settlements. This marked a turning point in Ankara's urbanisation path, one that redefined its spatial organisation and socio-economic dynamics. The outcomes of this urbanisation process, however, have been highly uneven, manifesting differently across the city's neighbourhoods depending on a variety of spatial and socio-economic characteristics.

This study, conducted within the framework of an ongoing PhD research project, seeks to analyse and interpret the spatial and temporal dimensions of Ankara's urban transformation from the 1970s to the 2020s. The principal aim is to evaluate how the city has evolved over the past half-century in terms of its physical form, housing structures, and social fabric, while also critically assessing the implications of these changes for long-term urban sustainability. Through the study's longitudinal methodology, which builds upon the foundational household surveys originally conducted by the British urban academician Geoffrey Payne in the 1970s, detailed empirical data on housing conditions, tenure security, and infrastructure access across various neighbourhoods were provided. Therefore, the study re-administers those surveys in the same locations approximately fifty years later, providing a unique opportunity to directly compare historical and contemporary data and thus uncover long-term trends in urban development. This approach offers valuable insights into the trajectories of rapid urbanisation and the extent to which urban integration and formalisation have occurred over time.

Four neighbourhoods were selected as case studies, each representing different characteristics of urban development, ranging from long-standing informal settlements and transition areas to formally planned and regulated residential zones. In addition to the replicated surveys, the study incorporates qualitative data collected through in-depth, semi-structured storytelling interviews with long-term residents, which offer rich narratives and localised perspectives on the socio-spatial transformation of Ankara, capturing the lived experiences of change, resilience, adaptation, and continuity across generations.

The study adopts a mixed-methodological framework, combining quantitative data analysis with qualitative interpretation, to achieve a holistic understanding of urban change. This integrated approach allows for a comprehensive examination of various dimensions, including shifts in housing quality, economic opportunity structures, and evolving patterns of social cohesion. Together, these elements provide an empirical foundation for assessing how changes in urban form and policy have influenced the overall liveability and sustainability of neighbourhoods. The research, therefore, sheds light on the enduring effects of policy decisions, socio-economic disparities, and informal urban practices by explicitly linking past urban conditions with present-day realities.

Keywords: rapid urbanisation; urban transformation; longitudinal study

Contact:

Sahinkaya, Cemre

Mainz University of Applied Sciences / University of Kassel
Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN2)

Advancing Open Microspatial Land Use Data for Sustainable Development: The Role of the Colouring Cities Research Programme

LARIMIAN, Taimaz; HUDSON, Polly; KIM, Mihyun; PALAIOLOGOU, Falli; KONIECZNY, Mateusz*

There is increasing demand for comprehensive microspatial land use data at the building and land parcel scale. Such data is essential for providing detailed insights into economic activities and is crucial for infrastructure management and planning aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Potential applications span a wide range, from the operation of national planning systems and transport networks to tackling challenges such as illegal mining, deforestation, and carbon emission modelling.

Despite this need, detailed national-scale spatial datasets remain rare. Land use information is often fragmented, incomplete, restricted in access, and lacks harmonised classification systems both within and across countries. This paper presents recent progress in developing low-cost, scalable methods to address these challenges and support cross-country standardisation.

The Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP) is an international academic initiative, launched in 2014, that promotes the release and harmonisation of open microspatial data to support the SDGs. It operates through a network of interoperable, open-source, open-data platforms managed at the national level by voluntary research consortia. The CCRP is decentralised, without formal agreements, and is overseen by academic partners who coordinate national platforms, CCRP Global Hubs, and technical and research groups. Since 2023, the programme has tripled national engagement and now collaborates with researchers in over 30 countries. It aims to pool research expertise and resources to minimise costs, reduce duplication, and accelerate problem-solving on common SDG-related challenges.

This paper focuses on how individual researchers within the CCRP are using national platforms to collaboratively develop and test prototype code for data capture, visualisation, and classification. It highlights the role of Colouring Britain, the CCRP's prototype platform, developed by researchers at the Alan Turing Institute and Loughborough University, as a testbed for land use data capture and classification.

The paper begins by outlining the key uses of spatial land use data in the UK, barriers to access, existing data sources, and inconsistencies in classification systems. It then describes the creation of a new national building footprint dataset for England and Wales, developed to initiate open spatial data sharing. A case study of Loughborough is presented, including data extraction, visualisation, and findings.

In the final section, the paper explores the development of open-source code to automatically align UK land use classifications with international standards, such as ISIC and NACE, to enable global comparability. It concludes by outlining the next steps for testing the new land use code with CCRP partners in the European Hub.

Keywords: Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP), Microspatial land use data, Open spatial data, Data standardisation

Contact:

Hudson, Polly
university of cambridge
United Kingdom

*Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN3)*

Does urban expansion in the Global South differ from the Global North?

KOOMEN, Eric; PRATOMOATMOJO, Nursakti Adhi; DE GROOT, Henri L.F.*

The Global South is urbanising rapidly as its cities attract rural inhabitants in search for a better living. Urban dynamics in the Global North are likely different as suburbanisation is still a major development, but there are also signs of reurbanisation. This begs the question how different urban expansion actually is in different regions around the globe.

Building on a newly developed spatial analysis framework we analyse urban expansion for a large set of capital cities around the world. Our framework characterises five different ways in which urban agglomerations expand in size. In addition to the commonly distinguished processes of infill, edge expansion, and outlying development, we also characterise two forms of urban development that we expect to be especially important in the fragmented urban landscape of the Global South: merging and joining. Merging is defined as the amalgamation of relatively small urban units into larger ones, while joining refers to the growing together of relatively large urban patches. In the latter case the total area of the initial urban patches is larger than the newly developed urban area that connects them.

In this research, we employ the latest release of the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) that provides a highly detailed, and fairly consistent rasterised account of urban development patterns since 1975. The spatial analysis process of our urban patch expansion framework consists of five stages: 1) detecting infill in urban voids; 2) identifying individual urban patches; 3) calculating the number of neighbouring patches for initial urban patches; 4) calculating the share of new urban patch areas relative to the total area of a new patch; and 5) calculating the share of borders with initial patches in relation to the total border length of the newly developed area.

Our research uncovers the dominant development processes per region and assesses how this dominance changes over time. In a subsequent panel regression analysis, we study the importance of various driving forces in steering these developments. More specifically we look at the relevance of economic and demographic indicators in addition to variables that describe the size and spatial patterns of the selected urban agglomerations. By separating the analysis for capitals in the Global South and North, we assess whether development trajectories differ between these regions.

Keywords: urban expansion, urban development patterns, spatial data analysis, panel regression

Contact:

Koomen, Eric
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam
The Netherlands

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN3)

A spatial inquiry of conflicts between densification, blue-green spaces, and urban flooding in Pune and Bangalore, India

GANGWAR, Druti*; BISWAS, Arindam

Background and need: A recent World Bank study indicates that hazardous flood zones in human settlements more than doubled from 1985 to 2015. Rapid urbanization has led to a constant rise in impermeable surfaces, blocking natural drainage systems and exacerbating surface runoff. These urbanization-induced changes amplify local vulnerabilities and manifest as risks, including recurrent and often severe urban flooding. In this context, nature-based solutions have reappeared as an opportunity to create resilient cities. Under this umbrella concept, the blue-green infrastructure (BGI) occurring as natural blue and green spaces has significant potential to mitigate urban flooding. The urbanization process, coupled with the fragmentation of blue and green spaces, has reduced BGI's capacity to absorb excess water during extreme rainfall events. Therefore, the hydro-ecological function of blue-green infrastructure in urban areas and their regional catchments needs to be considered while planning for urban development.

Study area and Data: Multiple studies have reported that over the last two decades, Indian metropolitan cities such as Chennai, Delhi, Hyderabad, Bangalore, and Mumbai have not just expanded but have also been experiencing recurrent urban flooding. The study area for this research is Pune and Bangalore, which are among Indian's 10 biggest Urban agglomerations. In 2024, the Pune Municipal Corporation (PMC) identified "flood-affected areas" based on recent monsoon impacts and citizen-reported data. Similarly, the Greater Bangalore Municipal Corporation (Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike, BBMP) classified "flood-vulnerable locations" in 2023 using remote sensing data and urban flood modeling. These in situ urban flooding datasets were obtained to carry out field investigations across both cities in locations where urban densification and urban flooding were conflicting. Simultaneously, the datasets indicating regional characteristics were extracted for these conflicting areas.

Methodology: The data acquired during the field investigation have been analyzed using micro-level spatial profiling techniques. The profiling of urban form and blue-green space characteristics was done using spatial variables such as built-to-unbuilt area ratios, extent of greenness, and the condition and presence of surface water bodies. These variables were mapped through visual observations and on-site photographic documentation. At the same time, the elevation (Digital Elevation Model), soil (typology), and precipitation (total annual rainfall) in these conflicting areas were extracted from secondary data sources and overlaid.

Results: The two-pronged approach provides a comprehensive overview of the spatial qualities of blue-green spaces in conflicting areas, i.e. urban flooding hotspots occurring in dense urban areas. The results reveal evidence to comment on the patterns of alterations of blue-green spaces in rapidly densifying urban areas. It also highlights spatial mismatches/ correspondence between areas of high impermeability and (in)adequacy of green or open areas. These findings offer evidence to comment on the causal relationship between urban densification, the disruption or absence of blue-green infrastructure, and the occurrence of urban flooding.

Keywords: Urban Densification, Urban Flooding, Blue-Green Infrastructure, Spatial Profiling

Contact:

Gangwar, Druti
Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee
India

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN3)

Mapping the Dynamicity of Urban Green and Concrete Spaces of Coimbatore City, India

*T K, Senthamizh; SHEKHAR, Sulochana**

Urban expansion in rapidly developing Indian cities has intensified the competition between green and concrete spaces, impacting environmental sustainability and urban livability. Urbanisation often changes a city's spatial, social, economic, and ecological conditions. Urban Green Space refers to various vegetation types in urban areas, like forests, trees, shrubs, wetlands, parks, etc. Urban Green Space provides several environmental benefits and services, like air purification, temperature reduction, biodiversity promotion, and quality urban life. Urban Concrete Spaces are impervious surfaces like buildings and roads, primarily concrete, asphalt, etc. Increasing concrete surfaces indicate urban expansion and sprawl, resulting in a temperature change, reduced soil permeability and groundwater recharge, impacts on air pollution, an altered urban environment, and urban flooding. This study investigates the spatio-temporal dynamics of green and concrete spaces in Coimbatore, covering 257 sq. km, India's 16th largest urban agglomeration and the second largest city in Tamil Nadu, following Chennai. Coimbatore has experienced notable urbanisation, particularly in the last few decades, including a substantial population and urban area increase, leading to land use, land cover changes, and industrial growth. The study spans between 2017 and 2025, utilising high spatial and temporal resolution, multi-spectral PlanetScope (3m) satellite imagery, an excellent source for vegetation monitoring in cloudy areas, as it increases the chance of acquiring a cloudless image.

The analysis employs machine learning and geoprocessing tools to extract and classify land use and land cover features. A multi-year temporal dataset was processed using GIS-based tools to map and quantify the changes in green and concrete spaces. The results reveal changes in green cover and built-up surfaces across the study period. The findings underscore significant urbanisation trends, indicating the conversion of natural landscapes into impervious zones, with implications such as heat stress, biodiversity loss, and challenges to environmental resilience. The study offers critical insights for urban planners, environmental regulators, and policymakers to improve green infrastructure planning for mitigating urban heat island effects and promoting sustainable urban development in metropolitan cities like Coimbatore, India.

Keywords: Urban Green Space, Urban Concrete Space, Green Infrastructure Planning, PlanetScope, Coimbatore

Contact:

T K, Senthamizh

Central University of Tamil Nadu

India

Track: Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North
Urban Dynamics in Global South and Global North (SN3)

Socioeconomic Segregation in Voicecall Networks: Analyzing the Impact of City Size in Chile and Brazil

SAMANIEGO, Horacio; VILLAGRA, Joaquin; FREIRE, Yerka; EVSUKOF, Alexandre*

Since the late 1990s, research on activity spaces has shifted the focus of segregation studies beyond residential areas, incorporating both temporal and spatial dimensions [1]. These expanded measures of segregation complement traditional residential segregation indices by capturing real-world social interactions. This shift enables a transition from place-based to people-based measures of segregation, offering a more dynamic understanding of social divides. Early work by Hägerstrand introduced a methodological framework to explicitly define the geography of social interactions, inspiring a steady stream of research across the social and natural sciences [2]. His contributions elevated this framework into a distinct sub-discipline known as Time Geography. Although initially overlooked due to the significant challenges of data management and analysis, Hägerstrand's approach has gained substantial traction in recent years. This resurgence is largely driven by advancements in technology, which have simplified the aggregation and analysis of individual trajectories, contextual factors, and infrastructural constraints across urban spaces [3]. For example, Alessandretti et al. [4] demonstrate, using mobile phone data, that despite the exploratory nature of human behavior, individuals tend to confine their activity spaces to a limited number of locations. This finding aligns with Dunbar's assertion of a cognitive limit—approximately 100 stable social relationships that an individual can maintain [5]. In this study, we explore how segregation, measured through voice call interactions, varies across cities of different sizes and socioeconomic status (SES) using mobile phone data in Chile and Brazil. By merging SES information with a Call Detail Records (CDR) dataset from a major mobile phone provider, we assess segregation patterns in voice call interactions across a gradient of city sizes in Chile. We analyze 12.5 and 1,258 million anonymized voice calls in Chile and Brazil respectively (representing social events) between reliable users to construct voice call networks for cities of different sizes. These networks are tagged with the SES of callers, call duration, and urban distance between callers, allowing us to characterize the nature of directed interactions based on SES. The SES of each user is estimated by determining their most probable residential location. Segregation is evaluated using a modified exposure index (E) applied across SES quintiles, providing insights into the dynamics of social interactions within and between socioeconomic groups. More specifically, we evaluate E between SES quintiles as following: $E_{\alpha\beta} = N / N_{\alpha}N_{\beta} \sum T (n_{\alpha} n_{\beta} / n_t)$ [6]. Here, α and β are SES, N total population. T is defined as the social space constructed from the egonet of diameter equal to three. These egonets were built for each user with known SES in the network. While city networks are generally sparse due to the dataset representing only a fraction of the market share, several network indices help describe the social structure of voice call interactions across cities and over time. For instance, call reciprocity remains large and consistent across cities. Assortativity by SES is positive in all networks, indicating that users tend to connect with others of similar socioeconomic status.

Keywords: Complex Networks, CDR data, time geography, segregation, exposure, mobile phone

Contact:

Samaniego, Horacio
Universidad Austral de Chile
Chile

Urban Structure and Policy

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form I (US1)

The Street Logic of Suburbs: Multiscalar Centralities and Street-Based Morphologies

*ARALDI, Alessandro**; *LOPES, Flavia*; *STAVROULAKI, Ioanna*; *FUSCO, Giovanni*;
BERGHAUSER PONT, Meta

Suburban territories continue to challenge sustainable urbanism. Their car-oriented layouts and fragmented public spaces contrast with contemporary demands for a more human-scaled, coherent, and dense urban fabric, as well as for models that minimize land artificialization. These conditions call for renewed suburban paradigms capable of generating suburban urbanities.

When examined through the lens of street networks, however, these landscapes reveal latent structures and potential centralities embedded within their existing morphologies.

This contribution develops the concept of a street logic of suburbs—an analytical and design framework linking multiscalar centralities to the morphological characteristics of suburban streets. Drawing on the DUT-funded Evolutive Meshed Compact City (EMC²) project, the research explores how suburban street systems can support more compact, connected, and walkable patterns of development.

The study focuses on five European metropolitan areas—Vienna, Gothenburg, Lille–Roubaix–Tourcoing, the French Riviera, and Versilia—representing a range of suburban morphologies. A combination of multiscalar configurational analysis and street-based morphometrics is applied to identify and characterize main street networks across scales.

Findings reveal that many suburban axes display strong configurational centrality but lack the morphological attributes that foster public life. Understanding this misalignment offers a foundation for rethinking suburban transformation, placing the street at the core of strategies for future, more urban, and sustainable suburban structures.

Keywords: Multiscalarity, Urban Morphology, Centrality

Contact:

Araldi, Alessandro

Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, ESPACE

France

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form I (US1)

An accessibility analysis of different urban structure types in the city of Berlin, based on the x-minute City concept

DROIN, Ariane; WURM, Michael; DEBRAY, Henri; TAUBENBÖCK, Hannes*

There is an increasing need to make cities more sustainable. One strategy is to improve the pedestrian and cycling accessibility to essential daily amenities. An urban planning concept used to measure the accessibility within cities is the concept of the "x-minute city". Here, 'x-minute' refers to the time needed to access all essential amenities. This concept has been applied to a variety of cities to compare accessibility due to their particular spatial distribution of traffic infrastructure and amenities. However, when this analysis is conducted at the level of whole cities, it tends to over-generalise the results to the entire urban area. Yet, cities are not uniformly composed: they consist of a combination of multiple types of urban structure that have evolved over time, each with their own distinctive characteristics. The urban morphology, the connectivity of the street network and the spatial distribution of amenities vary greatly depending on these types of urban structures and on where they are located within cities. To date, the impact of urban structure types on pedestrian accessibility, using the measure of x-minuteness, has only been studied for a few specifically selected and very distinctive urban structure types. A comprehensive study researching accessibility at the city level, differentiated by types of urban structures, has yet to be conducted. The city of Berlin offers a dataset at the block level with information on the occurring urban structure types for the whole city. Using network analysis, we calculated the pedestrian accessibility to 16 amenities of daily essential needs (e.g. pharmacy or supermarket) across seven different residential urban structure types. Our results demonstrate that accessibility is highly dependent on the underlying urban structure type. For example, while the average x-minuteness for the city of Berlin as a whole is of 30.5 minutes, we can show that the mean x-minuteness for areas consisting of Wilhelminian-period block-edge development (historical type of urban structure dating from the end of the 19th century) is of only 13.5 minutes. This differs significantly from the urban structure type Single-family homes with private greening which showcases an average of 36.5 minutes. Moreover, we find not only that the average accessibility varies between different urban structural types, but also that the spatial distribution of the amenities is clearly distinctive for each type of urban structure. This kind of analysis can specifically identify areas with insufficient accessibility by highlighting which amenities lack good access in each urban structure type. These insights can support urban planners and city councils by pinpointing where pedestrian accessibility can be improved to generate more sustainable, liveable and pedestrian-friendly cities.

Keywords: accessibility, urban structure, morphology, x-minute-City, routing

Contact:

Droin, Ariane

Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg

Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form I (US1)

Improving the quality of building change detection based on geospatial vector data matching

*RAIMBAULT, Juste; PERRET, Julien; OLTEANU-RAIMOND, Ana-Maria**

Quantifying urban dynamics through building change is an important component to plan for sustainable cities, in particular regarding issues related to densification and accessibility. While methods based on remote sensing images and machine learning on raster data have been recently thriving, methods based on change detection in vector data can offer a high resolution description of changes enriched with several attributes, but yet remain underexplored in the literature. Indeed, change detection in geospatial vector data using matching algorithms still faces technical difficulties. This contribution investigates how to improve the quality of such approaches.

More precisely, we tackle different complementary issues: (i) the lack of ground-truth datasets, for which we build a collaboratory annotation web platform, on which users annotate simultaneously observed changes in aerial imagery and expected matching links in corresponding vector datasets; (ii) the various performance of existing algorithms depending on the urban context, which we handle by introducing a novel multi-modelling algorithm combining geometric matching of areas (performing better on links between single features) with multi-criteria matching (performing better on multiple links); (iii) the dependence of algorithm performance to hyperparameters, which we optimise on ground truth data obtained in the first step (F-score indicator) using the OpenMOLE platform and a NSGA2 genetic optimisation algorithm.

We illustrate the application of the approach in a comparative manner on two different European urban areas: Strasbourg, France, and Dortmund, Germany. First results show a significantly better performance of the optimised multi-modelling algorithm, compared to optimised versions of single algorithms, and to versions with default parametrisations. Country differences in optimised parameters do not seem to be significant, suggesting a potential genericity of the approach. Future work will include the scaling of the approach to larger areas, and its test on more various types of urban form.

Keywords: Building change detection; Geospatial vector data matching; Ground-truth data; Hyperparameters optimisation

Contact:

Raimbault, Juste

IGN-ENSG

France

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form I (US1)

Urban Block Archetypes for Circular Urban Regeneration: A Geospatial Framework for Comparative Analysis Across European Cities

*SAMEEKSHA Madhav**

As European cities seek pathways toward sustainable urbanisation, the circular economy has emerged as a guiding principle for reducing resource consumption and environmental impacts. The transition toward a circular economy in cities demands spatially grounded approaches that can capture and respond to the complexities of the built environment. Among the various scales of analysis, the urban block sitting between the granular scale of buildings and the systemic view of entire urban regions, provides a spatially coherent unit that integrates land use, built form, and infrastructural systems. Using the urban block as the analytical entry point allows for targeted interventions and context-sensitive strategies that align with circular economy principles such as reuse, adaptability, and density optimisation. Anchoring circularity at this meso-scale facilitates integrated assessments of material stocks, socio-economic conditions, and environmental risks.

While increasing attention is being paid to circularity in the built environment, the literature remains fragmented across scales. Most existing analyses focus either on the building level where life cycle data is available or on macro-level indicators at city or regional scales. This leaves a conceptual and operational gap at the block level, where spatial, material, and social dimensions intersect. Existing archetype classifications are typically city-specific and focus on energy or microclimatic modelling, often neglecting key circularity factors such as reuse potential, embedded materials, and socio-cultural values. A need exists for transferable, data-driven typologies that can support comparative analysis and decision-making across diverse urban contexts.

To address this, the present study introduces a geospatial methodology for creating urban block archetypes aimed at supporting circular regeneration. The classification approach uses harmonized spatial datasets including cadastral data, building attributes, land use, and construction age to group blocks based on their morphology, functional mix, and circularity potential. Key indicators include density, land use diversity, compactness, accessibility, and exposure to environmental risks. Clustering techniques are applied across several European urban agglomerations to identify recurring spatial patterns and characterize representative block types.

These archetypes provide a scalable framework for further analysis, including scenario modelling, policy testing, and life cycle assessment. By capturing both commonalities and differences across cities, the typology allows for a more nuanced understanding of how local conditions shape the feasibility and impact of circular strategies. The archetypes also serve as building blocks for developing simplified digital models of urban form, supporting more efficient and participatory planning tools.

The study contributes to ongoing efforts to integrate circular economy principles into spatial planning by offering a methodological foundation for analysing and comparing urban blocks as drivers of transformation. It highlights the value of using open spatial data and interoperable tools to support urban sustainability and decarbonization goals. Ultimately, the framework strengthens the link between urban morphology and circularity, providing operational guidance for planning, design, and policy in support of resilient, inclusive, and resource-efficient urban futures.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Urban Block Archetypes, Geospatial Analysis, Sustainable Urban Regeneration, Spatial Typologies, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Material Flow, Data-Driven Planning, Urban Morphology, Clustering Methods

Contact:

Sameeksha Madhav

University of Liege, Belgium

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Dynamics (US2)

Understanding Regional Spatiotemporal Changes in 3D Building Density and Built-Up Expansion

BRASSEUR, Amandine; GONG, Suxia; COURARD, Luc; TELLER, Jacques*

To align with the principles of sustainable development, it is essential to understand the dynamics of urban transformation, particularly the mechanisms of building renewal, renovation and new construction. Monitoring the evolution of building volumes and the expansion of constructed area enables a better understanding of urban densification dynamics and supports evidence-based spatial planning. To address this question, this study integrates cadastral and LiDAR data to quantify residential building volume changes in Wallonia (Belgium) between 2010 and 2020. The primary reference data is derived from official regional cadastral records, which primarily describe parcel-level attributes rather than building characteristics. For residential buildings, critical data gaps exist, such as missing building types or floor counts. To address these gaps, we integrate LiDAR-derived height data (Digital Surface Models and Digital Terrain Models) with calibrated cadastral records for 2010 and 2020, ensuring accurate classification of building typology and volume estimation. The volume is estimated for each building by multiplying the footprint area by the building height. The 3D building density is calculated by dividing the sum of the building volumes within the zone of interest by the area of the zone of interest. In addition, the 3D density index is mapped at multiple scales to compare the differences in spatial development of the Belgian territories. Lastly, economic factors such as land values and house prices, as provided by the Federal Public Service Finance (Belgium), are included to study their influence on the expansion and renewal of the urban building stock.

Keywords: 3D density index, Spatiotemporal changes, Densification, Expansion, Land values

Contact:

Brasseur, Amandine
University of Liège
Belgium

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Dynamics (US2)

Intra-urban Patterns across the Globe: The 'what' and the 'where' of urban structures and planning practices in their geographical contexts

*DEBRAY, Henri**; *LEMOINE-RODRÍGUEZ, Richard*; *TAUBENBÖCK, Hannes*

Urbanization is an ongoing planetary process. With the ongoing rapid pace of urbanization and the conjunctural environmental and social pressures, better understanding of cities at a global level becomes an ever more pressing matter. In that research agenda, urban structures (here understood as the patterns of composition and configuration of the built and natural urban space) plays the role of a cornerstone. On the one hand, urban structures are a by-product of (even unconscious) societal choices accumulated over time. On the other hand, urban structures have direct impacts on both cities' inhabitants and the environment. Therefore, the study of urban structures lies at the core of understanding how these have been shaped and how in turn, they shape urban phenomena.

In this context, the constitution of a globally consistent repertory of urban structures is of prime interest to promote systematic analysis of their relations to urban planning and urban phenomena. While remote sensing and geospatial data support an increasing body of research on this topic, these studies have been generally limited in their spatial coverage due to different data and computational bottlenecks. For these reasons, the current focus of research is on urban structures that can be considered salient due to their functional, cultural or aesthetic value. Yet, beyond these types of urban structures lies a vast typology that could enable a more complete and more detailed picture of how urban structures affect their populations and our environment. In the present study, we aim at constituting and analyzing a typology of urban structures as comprehensive and global as possible.

A novel unsupervised clustering approach based on deep learning, the SCAN+RUC framework, is employed on a global Land-use-Land-cover classification product, namely the Local Climate Zones for more than 1500 cities. This dataset describes the urban fabric in terms of morphological characteristics and land cover types (built-up, vegetation, open land, water) at a resolution of 100m. In this study, patches of 3.2km*3.2km of this product are used as a proxy for representing the composition and the configuration of the urban fabric at an aggregated meso-scale. With this, we extract a typology of 138 intra-urban pattern types representing statistically different structures of urban space at a meso-scale.

Analyzing the compositional and configurational specificities of these types, and their global geographical distributions, we identified urban structures associated with specific urban planning practices. From these, we analyze the regions where particular urban structures are present and discuss the dynamics leading to their geographical spreads. With these results, we aim to contribute to debates on the viability of urban structures, urban planning practices and policies across different geographical and cultural contexts.

Keywords: Intra-Urban Patterns, Global urban structures

Contact:

Debray, Henri
University of Würzburg
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Dynamics (US2)

Towards the characterization of human settlement structure dynamics using the Global Human Settlement Layer and time series of landscape metrics: A study from Poland, 1975-2020.

KRASNODĘBSKA, Katarzyna; UHL, Johannes H.; CARIOLI, Alessandra; ŚLESZYŃSKI, Przemysław;
PESARESI, Martino*

Spatial and temporal characterization of human settlements over large areas is essential for a wide range of applications. Settlement classification supports the monitoring of sustainable urban and rural development, while the analysis of settlement trends enables cause-and-effect assessments that link territorial management and spatial planning to the impacts of implemented policies and activities. This work therefore aims to leverage novel global, multitemporal data on built-up surfaces and population distributions within an integrated framework for detailed characterization of human settlements over time.

Specifically, we use Earth-observation based gridded built-up surface and census-derived gridded population estimates from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) project of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre. The GHSL data offer multivariate global data on the built environment and population, consistently enumerated at 100-meter spatial resolution, covering almost five decades. The multivariate nature of GHSL data facilitates the monitoring of large-scale changes in the distribution of population and built-up surface in a joint manner.

In this study, we use GHSL data representing estimates of built-up surface and population for the period 1975–2020, at five-year intervals, and Local Administrative Units (LAU) as a spatial unit of analysis. We first discretize the continuous built-up surface and population densities into quantile-based classes, and categorize the area of interest based on their cross-tabulation. This way, we identify for example highly built-up areas with high, or low population density, modelling the interaction between population and built-up surface. For the areas covered by each of these classes, for each point in time, we observe the absolute changes in built-up surface and population, and derive a wide set of landscape metrics to describe their spatial structure, i.e., their composition and spatial configuration across space and time.

This two-fold assessment, which considers quantitative and spatial changes in human settlements enables the identification of areas undergoing substantial changes in land development from a novel, multi-faceted perspective. The proposed framework allows for the integrated quantification of these developments for each local government unit (LAU). Assessment at the LAU level facilitates data-driven classification using clustering methods, linking derived classes to socio-economic data, and ultimately, a joint assessment of settlement trends using additional indicators.

By using global, spatially and temporally consistent data, the proposed approach is universal and allows for flexible selection of case studies. We tested proposed approach on the example of Poland: a country with strong socio-economic development dynamics in recent decades and the complex settlement structure of urban and rural areas; and are currently working on extending the proposed approach to larger geographic scopes.

Keywords: Human Settlement Dynamics, Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL), Landscape Metrics, Built-up surface, Population

Contact:

Krasnodębska, Katarzyna

Institute of Geography and Spatial Organization Polish Academy of Sciences
Poland

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Dynamics (US2)

Urbanization did not start with the launch of Landsat: Geospatial data and modelling strategies for the long-term assessment of urban dynamics

UHL, Johannes H.; LEYK, Stefan; PESARESI, Martino; BURGHARDT, Keith; DIJKSTRA, Lewis; KEMPER, Thomas*

The anthropogenic footprint on Earth, including transportation networks and settlements such as cities, towns, and villages, has been shaped over the course of centuries and more. However, our quantitative knowledge of these long-term landscape changes is scarce, due to a lack of digital geospatial data reflecting land use and land cover (LULC) prior to the era of operational remote sensing and digital cartography.

We argue that for an enhanced understanding of longer-term landscape transformation processes such as urban growth, conurbation and (sub-)urbanization, as well as urban and rural land use dynamics, commonly used remote-sensing based LULC data from recent decades only provide a limited picture. As a consequence, derived trends may disregard important long-term context, and extrapolated future development pathways may lack statistical robustness due to limited historical data available for modelling. To address this shortcoming, researchers have started to use geohistorical data sources such as scanned and georeferenced historical maps, historical overhead imagery, authoritative building and road register data providing information on construction epochs, historical gazetteers and other structured and unstructured data sources. Such data are increasingly available in openly accessible, digital data formats, and recent advances in Artificial Intelligence and data processing and integration capabilities have further catalyzed such efforts.

Herein, we summarize our recent advances in curating, integrating, and providing analysis-ready geospatial data that enables researchers, planners, and practitioners to gain quantitative knowledge on long-term landscape changes during the 20th century, ranging from national-level to global geographic scope, encompassing long-term changes in built-up areas, road networks, land cover, and populated areas.

We discuss novel data sources such as HISDAC (Historical Settlement Data Compilation) that leverages building and property-level microdata including construction year information to model historical built-up areas, building densities and settlement extents using spatial aggregation techniques. HISDAC has been produced for the conterminous US (HISDAC-US) and Spain (HISDAC-ES), and has recently been extended to the Netherlands (HISDAC-NL). We briefly discuss ongoing efforts that apply HISDAC data, including long-term population disaggregation and rural-urban continuum modelling, as well as modelling of the age and expansion patterns of urban street networks.

Moreover, we outline how we employ scanned and georeferenced historical maps and historical aerial imagery for large-scale, retrospective change analysis of forest and settlement extents, integrated with modern remote-sensing based data, and showcase data integration efforts of gridded population data and long-term land use models for refined historical population modelling at 1-km resolution, at global scale since 1900.

Keywords: Long-term settlement mapping, historical maps, road network evolution, data integration, degree of urbanisation

Contact:

Uhl, Johannes
European Commission
Italy

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Planning (US3B)

Simulating Urban Futures: Evaluating Spatial Planning Strategies As A Roadmap For NNLT 2050

*CHAKRABORTY, Anasua**; *TELLER, Jacques*

Achieving No Net Land Take (NNLT) by 2050 is a key planning objective across many European regions. In Wallonia (Belgium), urban development continues to pressure land resources, despite efforts promoting densification. Historically shaped by suburban expansion and decentralised governance, the region faces ongoing challenges in limiting land take. While business-as-usual (BAU) projections anticipate a gradual decline in expansion, recent trends suggest this may be overly optimistic. To assess the long-term impact of spatial policies, this study contrasts BAU with a Growth-As-Usual (GAU) scenario, assuming constant development pressure and resulting in over 27,000 hectares of additional built-up land by 2050.

We apply a Multinomial Logistic Regression–Cellular Automata (MNL-CA) model to simulate future urban development in Wallonia under GAU conditions and evaluate two planning strategies aimed at achieving NNLT: Densification Only (DO) and Centralities (C). The DO scenario restricts all new development to existing urban areas through infill and vertical densification. The Centralities scenario permits both densification and limited expansion within a network of selected urban nodes, chosen for their infrastructure, accessibility, and strategic role.

Both alternatives significantly reduce land take compared to GAU. The DO scenario halts expansion entirely by reallocating growth within existing built environments. However, it leads to spatial saturation in many municipalities by the mid-2030s, raising concerns about infrastructure capacity, service stress, and social equity. The Centralities scenario results in a more balanced spatial distribution and reduces total land take to around 6,100 hectares by 2050. It also preserves rural landscapes and avoids overburdening specific areas.

Beyond aggregate outcomes, we analyse the spatial distribution of benefits and burdens. The DO strategy disproportionately favours municipalities with available capacity, potentially widening disparities in housing and investment. In contrast, the Centralities approach concentrates growth and infrastructure in designated nodes, potentially limiting opportunities in non-selected areas.

Our findings indicate that while both DO and Centralities offer pathways toward reducing land take, each involves trade-offs in feasibility, equity, and governance. Effective implementation requires not only strong spatial modelling but also coordination across planning levels and sectors. This study underscores the value of scenario-based modelling for guiding strategic decisions in urban and regional planning and highlights the need to balance environmental goals with issues of access, fairness, and territorial cohesion.

Keywords: Urban densification, NNLT2050, Spatial planning, Sustainable urban development

Contact:

Chakraborty, Anasua
University of Liege
Belgium

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Planning (US3B)

Regionalise it – but how? Interdisciplinary insights into inter-municipal land management in Germany amid economies of scale and territorial governance constraints

HÄFNER, Lukas*

Inter-municipal cooperation has become an increasingly prevalent governance strategy across Europe, enabling municipalities to jointly provide services for mutual benefit. These cooperative arrangements manifest in diverse and evolving forms, shaped significantly by political leadership and administrative traditions. A primary rationale behind such cooperation is the pursuit of economies of scale; however, these gains are counterbalanced by substantial transaction costs and institutional risks borne by the individual municipalities. Land management, as a fundamental aspect of municipal land policy, enables local authorities to actively govern the distribution of land. It involves complex negotiations between public and private actors and encompasses a range of land types, including residential, commercial, infrastructure, and compensation areas. While land management is frequently framed as a tool to curb land consumption, its inter-municipal implementation is increasingly scrutinized, particularly regarding its effectiveness in reducing land consumption.

Bringing together perspectives from public management and spatial planning, this study adopts an interdisciplinary lens to examine inter-municipal cooperation and land management in the context of decentralized governance and sustainable settlement development. Specifically, it applies a second-generation rational choice approach—the Institutional Collective Action (ICA) Framework—to address two central research questions: What motivations and institutional structures characterise inter-municipal cooperation and land management in varying spatial contexts? To what extent do factors such as population density, involvement of private actors, and public funding programs influence their emergence?

The empirical analysis is based on 64 case studies derived from a nationwide online survey, further enriched by publicly available statistical data. These cases were analyzed using fuzzy-set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA) to identify patterns and subsequently deepened through semi-structured expert interviews. The findings underscore the predominance of economic considerations in driving inter-municipal cooperation and land management. Furthermore, they reveal the critical role of targeted incentives in overcoming institutional and financial barriers, particularly in rural contexts. Two principal patterns emerge from the analysis:

In high-density municipalities, strong personal leadership constitutes a central enabling factor. Additionally, external support through funding programs or strategic engagement with private actors contributes significantly to the effectiveness of inter-municipal cooperation and land management.

In rural municipalities, where the relative benefits of cooperation are often outweighed by transaction costs, the emergence of inter-municipal arrangements depends heavily on the involvement of private actors, access to funding, knowledge transfer mechanisms, and committed local leadership.

These findings contribute to a broader understanding of cooperation dynamics in multi-level yet decentralised governance systems. While municipalities in urbanised areas are more likely to engage in cooperation due to spatial development pressures and reduced reliance on external incentives, rural municipalities require a combination of supporting conditions to render cooperation viable.

In conclusion, the study highlights the need to design incentive structures and compensation mechanisms that mitigate dependency on private actors and better align inter-municipal cooperation with the normative goals of sustainable and integrated spatial development.

Keywords: inter-municipal cooperation, land management, regional governance, ICA-framework, fsQCA

Contact:

Häfner, Lukas
University of Kassel, Germany,

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Planning (US3B)

In Pursuit of Net Zero – Land Take Policies in Europe

*PETER, Lacoere; ANDREAS, Hengstermann; HARTMANN, Thomas**

Reducing land take is a major challenge for spatial planning in many European countries. Therefore, the European Commission has introduced the target of „No Net Land Take“ (NNLT) in the Roadmap to a Resource-Efficient Europe (2011) (European Commission 2011). NNLT aims to avoid, minimize, or compensate any new land take by 2050 (European Commission 2021). This ambitious target requires translation into national policy and legislation. Various countries have already taken measures to curb land consumption (Hartmann/Hengstermann/Jehling et al. 2025). In many countries, the discussion is shaped by an instrumental approach (Eichhorn/Adam/Schürholt et al. 2024). However, it is often observed that such an instrumental approach tends to disregard the international perspective.

This contribution presents and discusses the political narratives and key mechanisms of action behind different such policies in different European countries, namely Belgium, England, France, the Netherlands, Austria, Switzerland, and Czechia. The overview is methodologically based on the institutional policy analysis by Peter Knoepfel et al. (Knoepfel 2007), which is related to actor-centered institutionalism. The analysis considers three elements: 1. The political perception of the problem; 2. The collective hypothesis about the cause of the problem; and 3. The main intervention. For each of these elements, the arguments of the dominant national discourses are presented. Whether the respective political assumptions (e.g., concerning the nature of the problem) align with actual spatial realities will not be questioned – political discourses may indeed deviate. Overall, this approach makes it possible to reveal the key mechanisms of action and the political narrative behind planning-related initiatives. The results are based on a focus group study (2019), findings from the international working group of the ARL on “Land Policies in Europe” (2020–2024), as well as complementary expert interviews and literature reviews.

The comparison of the different countries shows how various national debates on land-take have often developed independently from the European NNLT policy. Also the significant role of property rights in the implementation of strategies to reduce land take can be demonstrated. Finally, while the original political objectives regarding land-take are often quite ambitious, it can be observed that they become increasingly flexible as they are translated into concrete measures. As a result, there is a growing polarization between socio-demographic growth and strict environmental goals in the current political context of many European countries.

Keywords: land take, comparative, land policy, Europe, NNLT

Contact:

Hartmann, Thomas
TU Dortmund University
Germany

Track: *Urban Structure and Policy*
Urban Structure and Policy: Planning (US3B)

Detecting Brownfield Development Cycles in Slovenia: An Approach to Support Circular Spatial Planning

*REBERNIK, Lea**

Functionally derelict areas, or brownfields, have gained increasing attention in Slovenia since 2015 due to their implications for sustainable land use, urban regeneration, and land recycling. Systematic monitoring began in 2017 with the first national database, identifying over 1,000 brownfield sites. Since then, the database has been updated twice (in 2020 and 2023), always with a combination of methods and sources – information from the municipalities, media and field visits, which ensures high quality data. This methodology enables spatial and temporal tracking of brownfield dynamics, and the datasets provide crucial insight into the scale, presence, and transformation of brownfields and are essential in addressing land take, urban sprawl, and biodiversity loss.

This study analyses brownfield development in Slovenia by combining spatial datasets from the three national databases with temporal-spatial analysis in R. The main objectives are: (1) to evaluate the evolution of brownfield monitoring and data management practices since 2015, and (2) to identify and characterize development cycles of brownfields across Slovenia. Recognising such cycles contributes to understanding land-use change processes and developmental practices, as well as supports planning strategies aiming to prioritize redevelopment over the expansion of build-up areas through greenfield investment.

The method involves harmonizing datasets across years to track site-level changes in brownfield status. We apply analysis to identify characteristics on three dominant trajectories: persistent brownfields (unchanged over time), emerging brownfields (newly identified), and redeveloping brownfields (removed from the inventory due to redevelopment). Additional GIS-based visualizations reveal spatial patterns, such as redevelopment clusters in urban centres and increasing brownfield emergence in peri-urban areas. These cycles indicate that brownfield dynamics are not static but respond to economic, policy, and spatial factors. Such findings highlight the necessity of continuous brownfield detection and monitoring, while open data platforms could enable responsive planning. Recognizing brownfield cycles allows planners to identify optimal intervention windows and tailor policy responses to specific spatial and temporal contexts.

Keywords: brownfield, land-use change, spatial-temporal analysis, sustainable spatial planning, Slovenia

Contact:

Rebernik, Lea
University of Ljubljana Faculty of Arts
Slovenia

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Scaling (US4A)

Radial scaling analysis and modelling of land use change in 1800+ world cities from 1975 to 2020

*RIVET, Thibaud; LEMOY, Rémi**

The ever-increasing urbanization of the world meets us with pressing socio-environmental challenges. The sprawl of human settlements all over the planet leads to losses of arable land and biodiversity, and increases flood risk and climate change. Considering the developing will of limiting urban sprawl (see for example the No Net Land Take objective), we aim to understand the fundamental structure and dynamics of cities.

We analyze how the internal structure of cities, in particular the share of built-up land, unfolds radially, from center to periphery, revealing patterns that shape urban dynamics. Since cities present a wide variety of sizes, scaling laws provide a powerful framework for modeling such behavior, capturing how a system's properties shift with its size. Viewing cities as systems and population as their defining scale, we study how cities sprawl as population grows, at the global scale.

We establish a robust radial scaling law which quantifies the connection between the distance to the city center and the share of built-up land, and how this relation scales with city size. This extends the homothetic scaling obtained in previous work to a global sample of cities and at different dates. We work on the 1860 cities of the world whose population is greater than 300,000 inhabitants in 2020. They present a large diversity of population size, topology, land use, urbanization policies and more. Nonetheless, the scaling law applies with surprising regularity. Looking at different points in time — from 1975 to 2020, with a 5 year step — allows us to analyze the evolution of this internal urban structure and scaling law of built-up land.

The dataset used in the study comes from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL), produced by the Copernicus service of the European Commission. It provides high-resolution and high-quality, globally consistent distributions of built-up areas, which we combine with the World Urbanization Prospect database from the United Nations for population statistics. For each city of choice and each date, we analyze this GHS BUILT-S raster layer at 100 meters resolution and compute the average built-up land share in concentric rings of 200 meters width around the city center. To ensure the viable comparability between cities, we rescale for each city the distance to the center proportionally to the square root of its population, using the largest one, Tokyo (with population 37 millions in 2020) as a reference.

We analyze the evolution of the mean rescaled profile, and observe that built-up land increases over time all along the center-periphery profile, even when the size effect is controlled by the homothetic scaling law. In linear scale (measuring absolute land change), the change is especially visible near the center, while it appears more clearly in the periphery on a semilog graph (measuring relative land change). This result means that the built-up surface per capita increases over time globally. We link this urban sprawl phenomenon with economic development and further analyze its geographical variations at national scale on the planet. This clearly questions the sustainability of urban expansion.

Keywords: land use change, urban scaling laws, urban expansion, built-up land

Contact:

Lemoy, Rémi

University of Rouen Normandy
France

*Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Urban Structure and Policy: Scaling (US4A)*

Power-law level-set percolation of urban land-cover in Europe – exploratory results

FAGUNDES, Renan Lucas; RYBSKI, Diego*

The analogy with percolation is used to describe transitions between fragmented and connected landscapes, or vice versa. Examples include deforestation and the disintegration of forests into increasingly smaller plots. Here, we study settlements as captured by urban land cover. However, cities and settlements have an influence on space that goes beyond their boundaries. Therefore, we model this influence with a function that decreases as a power law with distance and with an exponent controlling this influence. To be more precise, each urban pixel “emits” this influence, so that larger settlements exhibit greater influence their surroundings. In our analysis, we model this influence as a scalar field and calculate it. For a given exponent, we chose a threshold for this intensity and check whether it is in a connected phase. By varying the threshold, we identified the critical threshold. We repeated the procedure while varying the exponent. Applying this approach to European countries, we found an exponential relationship between the values of the exponent and the influence threshold. Higher values of the exponent are associated with lower critical thresholds. We extract the exponential relationship for several European countries. To understand the implications of the exponential relationship between the influence exponent and the field threshold require further research, theoretically formalizing the problem according to the level-set percolation theory.

Keywords: urban percolation level, urban influence field, urban growth

Contact:

Fagundes, Renan Lucas

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Critical Landscape Phenomena
Urban Structure and Policy: Scaling (US4A)

The Scaling of Building Height with Population and Land Use: A Three-Dimensional Perspective

ZHANG, Peiran*

Traditionally, urban development is studied in terms of land use in two-dimensions, largely ignoring the third dimension. However, building height is crucial because it enhances the availability of interior space of cities. Using a newly released global building height dataset of almost 3000 cities across 42 countries, we develop a scaling model to simultaneously examine the relationship between urban population size and both horizontal and vertical urban extents. Contrary to expectations, we find that the residents of most urban systems do not significantly benefit from vertical dimension, with population accommodation being primarily driven by horizontal extent. The associations with country-level external indicators demonstrate that the benefits of horizontal extent are more pronounced in urban systems with more extreme size distribution (most population concentrated in few cities). Moreover, building classification tests confirm the robustness of our findings across all building types. Our findings challenge the intuition that building height and high-rise development significantly contributes to accommodation, calling for targeted policies to improve its efficiency beyond land use.

Keywords: urban scaling, building height, land use

Contact:

Zhang, Peiran

The Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Density (US4B)

Uncovering Dutch Residential Development Processes

*CLAASSENS, Jip**; *KOOMEN, Eric*; *ROUWENDAL, Jan*

Cities grow by extending at their edges and by densifying their existing urban fabric. The latter process has advantages in terms of saving open space, allowing more efficient use of space, sustaining higher amenity levels and limiting travel, but also threatens urban green spaces and results in (over)crowding. The balance between these impacts depends to a large extent on how urban areas are redeveloped. This paper looks at the dominant form of urban redevelopment in the Netherlands: the addition of new residences within existing urban areas.

We investigate the complexity of residential (re)development by analysing 30 million housing-stock mutations recorded in the national building administration for 2012-2025. By combining several spatial data layers, we identify four processes: (1) replacement (demolition followed by new construction on the same parcel), (2) new build on unbuild land, (3) within-building additions or splits, and (4) transformation of non-residential buildings to residential. The results show that three-quarters of the net addition of around one million dwellings took place within the existing urban fabric. Replacement accounts for a growing share of net additions over time, while new build development slightly declines. High-density neighbourhoods—just 7 % of Dutch land—host five times more replacement additions per square kilometre than low-density areas. Regression models reveal that housing growth per neighbourhood correlates positively with higher social rent shares, high densities of urban amenities, and a higher share of protected heritage areas, but negatively with potential available land, indicating that scarcity incentivises densification. Effect sizes differ markedly across density categories and development processes; for example, the positive impact of urban attractiveness on transformation and within-building additions strengthens as neighbourhood density falls.

The study contributes by: (1) providing a reproducible micro-scale method to detect residential development processes; (2) demonstrating that densification is a substantial—and still growing—component of Dutch housing supply; and (3) offering policy-relevant evidence that densification succeeds mainly in neighbourhoods with historic building stock, high amenity levels and limited expansion space. These insights support spatial strategies that blend targeted infill with selective outward growth to meet future housing demand.

Keywords: Residential development processes, Densification, urban development, netherlands

Contact:

Claassens, Jip

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

The Netherlands

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Density (US4B)

Developing a Multidimensional Characterisation of Built Density for Evidence-Based Urban Planning

COLICCHIA, Hugo; DELHAYE, Steve; LE FORT, Barbara; WAYENS, Benjamin; WOLFF, Elénone*

Over the last decade, significant advances have been made in the systematic and quantitative characterisation of urban form, for which tools and indicators were developed. At the same time, urban planning authorities have remained poorly equipped both theoretically and practically for facing contemporary urban challenges, such as densification. Built density is still often apprehended through simple surface-based indicators such as floor area ratio (FAR) and building coverage ratio (BCR). Although these indicators are easily intelligible, many papers have argued that they cannot totally encompass the multifaceted nature of density, especially in complex urban landscapes. Yet, too little attempt was made to link tools developed in the academic literature and urban planning practices.

Our communication proposes a simple methodological framework to characterise built density using a typological approach. The method is intended to be fully reproducible and easily adaptable to many cities (for the resulting 'density types' are defined on local data) in order to be adopted in planning decision-making. Our work is conducted in the context of the new Brussels Land Use Plan drafting, in collaboration with the Brussels Planning Agency.

First, we identify a series of indicators able to account for the many dimensions of built density and compute them. Second, we perform a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) on these indicators to create uncorrelated multidimensional variables that we map, describe and define as components of density. Third, we apply a clustering algorithm on the most informative components and map the resulting clusters, i.e. density types. Our preliminary results show that considering more indicators of built density than FAR and BCR helps at differentiating more complex situations and nuancing our view on the urban landscape. In the context of regulating future densification and planning de-densification of certain areas in Brussels, we initiate a reflexion on how a quantitative multidimensional understanding of built density can translate into tangible urban planning policies.

Keywords: Densification, Built Density, Urban Form, Principal Component Analysis

Contact:

Colicchia, Hugo
Université libre de Bruxelles
Belgium

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Density (US4B)

Predicting incremental densification – a parcel-level model of unplanned urban dynamics

*EHRHARDT, Denise**; *EICHHORN, Sebastian*; *KOOMEN, Eric*; *JEHLING, Mathias*

Cities are increasingly under pressure to accommodate growing populations, leading to a rising demand for new housing. While urban expansion and large-scale brownfield conversions continue to play a role, much of this demand is met by small-scale, incremental densification, particularly in suburban areas. These subtle yet frequent changes are considered to alter urban form and increase population densities in locations often characterized by limited infrastructure capacity. For urban planning this poses significant challenges as it contradicts long-term assumptions about where development is likely to occur. However, two key issues complicate insights into incremental densification: first, small-scale processes often take place within existing building right and outside the scope of formal planning and are poorly captured by existing statistics—especially in contexts like Germany; second, estimating future processes is inherently difficult, as decisions to densify depend heavily on individual preferences of landowners, which frequently diverge from market-driven logic. Addressing these challenges is essential for creating more resilient and responsive planning frameworks for incremental densification.

In this contribution, we thus present an approach that allows us to measure and predict incremental densification. As a case, we look at densification in suburban areas of the city of Munich in the period of 2013-2023 to then predict the probability for future development at the level of individual plots. We measure incremental changes based on building footprints and train a random forest model. As predictor variables we use high-resolution socio-demographic data, accessibility and neighbourhood indicators as well as plot and building characteristics, e.g. land prices, age of residents, type of owner, the built-up ratio or the year of construction of existing buildings. The trained model is then used to predict probabilities for future development from 2023 onwards. We develop two models: Whether incremental densification takes place or not (classification problem) and how much new floor area can be expected on a parcel (regression problem). The results show a 10% overall increase of floor area in suburban areas of Munich. The predominant process is replacement of single-family homes by apartment blocks. For the classification if densification takes place or not, we achieve an overall accuracy of 0.77 and a ROC-AUC of 0.86. The initial floor area ratio, the size and form of the parcel as well as the year of construction of the existing building showed to be important predictors in the model. The prediction of new floor area yields weaker results, with an R^2 value of 0.27. For the prediction, we applied a robust estimation strategy and opted to first predict the probability for future development per parcel and use a factor derived from the empirical data to derive an average increase of floor area. Overall, the results are highly promising for estimating future densification in suburban areas, providing an evidence-based support for strategic planning.

Keywords: densification, random forest, prediction, parcel-level

Contact:

Ehrhardt, Denise
Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Climate (US5)

From Data to Design: Data-driven Climate Adaptation in Urban Hesse

*BENZ, Susanne**; *JEHLING, Mathias*; *OTTO, Iris*; *DIETRICH, Lisa*; *WURSTHORN, Sven*; *KRIKAU, Svea*;
SCHENK, Andreas; *BOEHNKE, Denise*; *HINZ, Stefan*; *GABRIEL, Raoul*; *KELLER, Sina*

Rising urban temperatures and densification demand strategic, context-sensitive responses. In partnership with the Hessian Ministry of Economics, Energy, Transport, Housing and Rural Areas (HMWVW), we developed a participatory, data-driven methodology on a 100 m grid that progresses through four stages.

Step 1: Identification of Universal Hot and Cold Spots. We identified persistent thermal extremes across Hesse using harmonized temperature metrics over a decade. This allowed us to distinguish universal hot and cold spots, which are not only statistically robust but also spatially consistent across day and night as well as heat stress and energy balance.

Step 2: Prioritization of Spatial Action Needs. To define where action is most urgently needed, we introduced a scoring system incorporating multiple dimensions: population density, presence of vulnerable facilities, local ventilation potential, temperature balance in the surrounding neighborhood, and the intensity of local heat or cold extremes.

Step 3: Assessment of Local Potentials and Deficits Using Urban Structure Types. To inform tailored interventions, each grid cell's potential for climate mitigation was evaluated relative to its structural context. Using high-resolution land cover segmentation (20 cm) and NDVI data, we quantified the degree to which a cell either contributes to or buffers against local heat stress. Crucially, these values were not assessed in isolation but benchmarked against other grid cells within the same urban structure type. This typology-sensitive lens ensures that interventions are both equitable and efficient.

Step 4: Mapping the Suitability of Mitigation Measures. Finally, we assessed the spatial suitability of six key mitigation strategies: green roofs, green facades, unsealing, vegetative shading, artificial shading, and vegetation health improvements. For each 100 m cell, suitability was derived from both physical characteristics and urban geometry. While conceptual guidelines for these interventions exist, our work moves toward spatially explicit implementation maps—bridging the gap between observation and action. By integrating multi-source data and structural typologies into a spatial decision-support tool, this project enables informed and site-specific climate adaptation planning for Hesse.

Keywords: climate adaptation, spatial planning, geodata, remote sensing, planning instruments, measures

Contact:

Benz, Susanne

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Climate (US5)

Evaluating Urban Heat-Induced Ecological Hazard Risks for Building Sustainable Cities: A Case Study of the Delhi Metropolis

UPRETI, Manjari; KUMAR, Amit*

Cities are experiencing extreme temperatures that exceed 50°C, resulting in severe consequences for biophilic conditions and a rise in mortality rates. The prevalence of impervious surfaces in urban environments disrupts natural energy flows and exacerbates Urban Heat Island (UHI) intensity. Delhi, with its rapidly urbanizing landscape and dense population (97.5% urban dwellers), is increasingly vulnerable to rising urban heat stress, particularly in the face of climate extremes. Therefore, the spatial dynamics of land surface temperature in conjunction with the morphological characteristics of the city were evaluated using the satellite-based remote sensing datasets. The study assessed differential UHI among the built-up and natural cover classes to estimate the role of natural landscapes in regulating Land Surface Temperature (LST) in different local climate zones (LCZ) utilizing long-term MODIS-based LST daytime and nighttime datasets. The differential UHI intensities were observed to be remarkably high in compact low-rise (1.8°C), compact mid-rise (1.7°C) in summer nighttime, followed by compact mid-rise (4.2°C), open lowrise (4.1°C), and heavy industry (3.6°C) in summer daytime.

Considering the rising surface heat stress, ecological infrastructure dynamics, urban morphological setup, and the green cover quality, the ecological hazard risk assessment has been performed using a multicriteria decision-making model known as Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) to identify the major hotspot of ecological concern. The study identified the ecologically fragile regions in the central northwest and east parts of Delhi, dominated by compact built-up clusters showing high LST, which reflects higher heat absorption capacity, reduced evaporative cooling, and increased health risks. The uneven distribution of green cover results in disparities in exposure to heat stress, with low-income areas in the northern, eastern, and western parts of the capital city suffering more with limited access to cooling infrastructure and healthcare. The findings highlight the importance of incorporating green infrastructure into urban planning to mitigate the adverse effects of urban heat stress and ecological fragility. The study strongly advocates for site-specific strategies by proposing a combination of nature-based solutions: green roofs, green walls, avenue plantations, parks, orchards, and green belts. Emphasizing native, heat-tolerant species like *Alstonia scholaris*, *Ficus religiosa*, and *Monoon longifolium*, these solutions are scalable and adaptable to urban centers. The present study emphasizes the development of healthy cities by ensuring universal access to safe, inclusive, accessible, green, and public spaces as per Sustainable Development Goal 11.5.

Keywords: Heat stress, Local Climate Zones, Ecological Hazard-risk, Green development framework, Nature-based solution, SDG

Contact:

Upreti, Manjari

Central University of Jharkhand

India

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Climate (US5)

The Potential Role of Food System Transformation at the Intersections of Landuse Change, Water and Climate Risks in Chennai (India)

WOIWODE, Christoph; A, Ramachandran

Chennai is the 4th largest urban agglomeration in India, with approx. 12 million inhabitants in the Chennai metropolitan area. Consequences of the rapid growth since the mid-1990s are witnessed in large scale land conversions often of agricultural land and water bodies, therefore aggravating climate change and disaster risks such as water scarcity and flooding, as well as food risks as observed during the pandemic. Governance of the region is equally changing dynamically, with the city and state governments currently formulating the third masterplan. Since the early 2000s, Chennai has witnessed a "millet revolution", a synonym used for numerous citizens initiatives to introduce organic food and promote 'non-conventional farming' and gardening. However, no strategic interventions have taken place such as integrating agroecology in the masterplan, or a regional food council or policy, even though there are multiple benefits of putting (peri)urban farming and gardening on the agenda. This paper brings together multi-year research on periurbanisation processes in the Chennai metropolitan region based on a bioregional definition of the periurban space. We elaborate on the intersection of an envisaged agroecology development pathway that highlights the land-water-food nexus. The authors are currently actively involved in several action research projects that support the implementation of such an agroecological development pathway.

Keywords: climate change risks, land-water nexus, adaptive governance, urban transformation, regional food system, Chennai

Contact:

Woiwode, Christoph

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Urban Structure and Policy: Climate (US5)

Using mobile phone data and GeoAI for heat relief areas allocation

BURATTINI FREIRE, Isabela; GOBATTI, Lucas; LEITÃO, João Paulo; BEHNISCH, Martin*

As a consequence of anthropogenic climate change, heatwaves are becoming more frequent and prolonged worldwide. This creates unprecedented challenges to cities, where the Urban Heat Island effect amplifies the negative impacts of heat on public health, urban well-being, education, labor productivity and critical infrastructure. However, current urban climate mitigation plans often overlook dwellers' behavioural responses to thermal stress alongside their daily activities. To address this gap, our study uses anonymized mobile phone data to analyze daily occupancy patterns and relative attractiveness during heatwave events at key urban leisure facilities, focusing on the city of Zurich as our study case. For this, we categorize leisure spaces into grey (shopping centers with seasonal active cooling), green (public parks and gardens), and blue (natural or artificial bathing sites) infrastructure. By comparing daily visitor numbers during heatwave days with long-term city-wide occupancy trends, we identify which facilities attract more visitors than expected under thermal stress. Our analysis reveals that bathing sites serve as primary heat retreat destinations in Zurich: when maximum daily temperatures exceed 30°C, bathing sites record 1.5 times more attractive days compared to parks, and 2.5 times more than shopping areas. To understand the spatial drivers of this behavior, we apply a spatially explicit explainable machine learning model. This approach captures complex, nonlinear, and threshold relationships between heat-related visitation patterns and urban spatial features. The results show that attractiveness to heat retreat areas is significantly influenced by longer waterfronts and distance from commercial centers, with areas located more than 2 km from such centers being particularly attractive. Our findings highlight the value of integrating urban big data for heat retreat areas allocation, which provides an evidence-based approach for informing adaptive urban design.

Keywords: Geospatial Artificial Intelligence, Blue-Green Infrastructure, Urban Resilience, Mobile Phone Data, Urban Attractiveness

Contact:

Burattini Freire, Isabela
Dresden University of Technology
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form II (US6A)

How do planning policies shape our cities? 3D Simulations of urban land-use planning regulations

*ABOLHASANI, Somaie**; *HERSPERGER, Anna*

Urban land-use planning regulations, including zoning, are critical policy instruments for managing urban development. While intended to guide cities toward collective goals, such as compactness, livability, and land-use efficiency, these regulations often produce complex and sometimes unintended urban form and land-use patterns. A key challenge is that these regulations are typically encoded in textual documents and linked to 2D zoning maps, yet their impacts are three-dimensional form and function of urban areas. Understanding beforehand how regulatory parameters can/will influence both urban form and urban function is crucial for creating more adaptive, equitable, and sustainable urban environments.

This study investigates the spatial implications of land-use planning regulations through a dynamic 3D simulation model that translates zoning documents into visual and measurable spatial scenarios. Using zoning maps and regulatory texts as input data, first, building regulations are extracted and classified from regulatory documents to simulate 3D buildings at Level of Detail 1 (LOD1). Developable zones are then subdivided into smaller parcels for future development. The classified regulations are applied to each parcel according to its specific zone. Recognizing that building regulations vary in the level of flexibility, multiple regulatory scenarios are simulated to model variations in building form and building function. Finally, these scenarios are assessed and discussed based on their impacts on mixed-use development, density of built volume and land consumption.

Sisslerfeld, the largest contiguous development reserve in northwestern Switzerland, is selected as the case study due to its diverse zoning areas and development potential. This site includes mixed-residential, residential, mixed-business, commercial, and industrial zones, each regulated by specific building parameters such as setbacks, Building Coverage Ratio (BCR), Floor Area Ratio (FAR), and building height. Regulations related to compatibility and use quantity further determine the combination and composition of permitted functions within a designated area.

To analyse the impact of these regulations, four building form scenarios and two building function scenarios are defined. Scenario simulations and visualizations are performed at the building level within a 3D environment using ArcGIS Pro. The results of the building form scenarios reveal how development preferences, prioritizing horizontal expansion or vertical growth, influence density of built volume and land consumption. In addition, the building function scenarios reveal how regulatory openness allows for both mono- and mixed-use development outcomes within the same zone.

This research demonstrates the analytical power of 3D simulation to make planning policies visible, interpretable, and comparable across different spatial configurations. By visualizing how regulatory frameworks can manifest in built form, the study contributes examining land-use regulations and their impact on urban development. It highlights the value of digital simulation in critically evaluating planning instruments, not only to assess efficiency and performance but also to identify spatial trade-offs and policy blind spots. Such tools can support more informed, anticipatory, and spatially responsive planning decisions in the face of complex urbanization dynamics.

Keywords: 3D urban modelling, Building regulations, Scenario analysis, Density, Mixed-use development.

Contact:

Abolhasani, Somaie

Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL
Switzerland

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form II (US6A)

Interaction of Spatial and Social Structure: A Geographically Weighted Approach to Modelling Housing Inequality

BRÁZDOVÁ, Anna; WINKLER, Lisa; FLEISCHMANN, Martin*

People can be characterised from many aspects, but one can tell more than most of the other - where they live. This research focuses on the interplay between the two aspects of cities - for one, their population and for the other, their built-up form - to understand the housing patterns in Czechia and the ability of different socio-demographic population groups to inhabit them. Both location and a type of urban development play a significant role in their lifestyle choices and accessibility to basic services and amenities, or dependency on individual transportation when moving around. However, not everyone is equally able to choose where to settle. The ongoing housing affordability crisis further restricts these choices, highlighting the urgent need for effective urban planning and housing policies that address growing inequalities.

While previous studies have often examined the socio-demographic structure of populations and the morphology of urban environments separately, this research addresses the gap by explicitly considering their interdependencies. It assesses the degree of inequality in access to various housing types at the neighborhood level, mapping these patterns at local and regional scales. Using spatially explicit architecture, the paper introduces new methods for modelling the relationship between socio-demographic factors and urban form to explore how socio-demographic indicators can predict the distribution of urban forms. By combining computational social science approaches, using recent census data, with morphological analysis through urban morphometrics, the research enables the quantification of both societal structure and the built environment, as well as the description of housing types from a data-driven built-form typology. Linking these indicators to specific neighborhoods allows for a comprehensive assessment of (in)equality of access to the desired place to live and the capability of different groups to make such a choice.

The findings offer a methodological contribution to modelling the relationship between socio-demographic factors and urban form, combining traditional machine learning with advanced spatial analysis techniques. While global models assume uniform relationships across entire datasets, geographically weighted models are inherently designed to capture geographic variations through localized analyses. This distinction is particularly important given the uneven spatial distribution of urban form classes. The results reveal clear spatial heterogeneity in the relationships between socio-demographic characteristics and housing typologies across Czechia, emphasizing the need for regionally tailored housing and urban planning policies. Geographically weighted models prove especially effective in capturing nuanced, location-specific dynamics that global models overlook. Furthermore, the case study of Czechia provides new insights into these dynamics at fine spatial scales, deepening the understanding of how social structures link to the built environment.

Keywords: urban form, geodemographics, spatial modelling, geographically weighted models

Contact:

Brázdová, Anna

Faculty of Science, Charles University

Czech Republic

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form II (US6A)

About the PA ratio for Urban Footprint

FABRI, Léandre; CARUSO, Geoffrey*

In urban planning, a simple uniform shape is favorable, indicating a compact city, while a complex shape signals high ecological fragmentation. Eventually, it is difficult to say whether a complex urban form is good or bad. There are no agreed reference values for the shape of cities with which we can confront case studies.

The P/A ratio is a common indicator of shape complexity. Measuring the complexity of a physical urban footprint is key to understanding the impact of urbanisation patterns. When the square root of the area is used as denominator, this complexity indicator is made independent of the size (area) of the patch and sometimes called 'shape-index'.

Our goal is to address those issues head-on by assessing the robustness of the 'shape-index' to the definition of patches and the aggregation methods. We suggest that instead of using arithmetic mean averages, we should look at the entire relationship between perimeter and square root of the area of all European cities.

This study analyses urban patches based on Urban Atlas 2018 (Copernicus), covering 785 functional urban areas (FUAs) in Europe. We classified 23 land cover categories into 2 classes to create the urban footprint with $u = 1$ for urban and $u = 0$ otherwise. As a measure for each city, urban patches are defined by 3 spatial analyses i, j and g.

i: using original patches

j: using merging patches that touch each other

g: all patches j are merged into a single patch

We propose to estimate the slopes directly from the elementary perimeters and areas in both i and j cases. Nevertheless, outlying values highly influence the fit j, we make those estimates after removing outliers called j.c, but we further demonstrated that a single estimated 'shape-index' is insufficient. Therefore, we compute a profile of estimations for subsets of increasing size along the area dimension, ranging from the initial values to the maximum.

We find that analysis j is more accurate than using analysis i and provides a better representation of reality, allowing more effective comparisons between cities. The j.c, which provided a good adjustment to fit the observed values, allows us to examine rural complexity by excluding outliers defined as the developed urban core. The estimated coefficient showed that the urban patch across Europe has a mean of 11.03, a good indicator of world cities. Complex urban patches are located together in Portugal around Porto, Belgium, Netherlands, and England, whereas simple urban patches are common in Spain, Turkey, Germany, and Bulgaria.

Providing readers with the possibility of obtaining a morphological indication depends on the profile. Notably, by looking at such profiles, we can understand the difference between the role of urban core patches and secondary patches that are more peripheral, often less complex, and smaller.

By systematically examining the urban footprint of 785 urban regions of different sizes, we provide a set of reference values and profiles that can be used for comparative studies at different scales and stages of urban growth. We think our novel approach is an important step towards a better understanding of the impact of more fragmented or complex urban footprints.

Keywords: fragmentation, landscape, urban, perimeter area ratio, shape-index

Contact:

Fabri, Léandre

University of Luxembourg, France

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Urban Form II (US6A)

From Anticipation to Reality? Tracing expected outcomes of land policy in urban form through a French-German cross-border data-model.

KLEINER, Caspar; JEHLING, Mathias*

Urban form is a key concern for sustainable urban development and climate change adaptation. Consequently, it has become a focus for policymakers over the past decades. While many countries implement land policies that pursue specific objectives in the built urban form, like density, accessibility, or lower land-take rates, their outcomes in the actually built urban form often remain only vaguely evaluated. Thus, challenging the effectiveness and legitimacy of land policies.

Consequently, this contribution focuses on tracing expected outcomes of land policies in the produced urban form. For this, the French-German border region serves as a study area due to its economic and demographic similarities and high level of interconnectedness. While policymakers in both countries have committed to sustainable urban development goals, they are employing different land policy approaches to achieve their goals. This leads to different outcomes that can be expected to materialize in the actual built urban form as a consequence of these land policies.

A fine-grained cross-border geo-data model is set up to evaluate expected outcomes of specific land policies in the built urban form in the two countries using a covariational approach. Based on harmonized and preprocessed national geo-data sources for streets, buildings and plots, a homogenous urban form model is set up at the building block level, i.e. development blocks grouping together plots and buildings in proximity that have been developed together. Further information on building types, ages, and location through accessibility are added to describe temporal and spatial patterns in the region. Identified land policies in the two countries are then assessed and evaluated based on their expected outcome that is shown in these dynamics and patterns from 1990 to 2020.

While quantifiable trends towards lower land-take rates are in line with the respective expected land policy outcomes, further outcomes of specific policies in built urban form vary significantly between the two countries, in time and by policy. Contradictory to the expected outcomes and land policy orientation, the data shows a distinct suburbanization process in the French part through the location evaluation. Simultaneously, share of building types shifts towards more multi-family housing in the French part in line with a specific land policy, while the German part is defined through an increase in low-density single-family house development. The variance in outcomes links to different approaches of implementing land policies in Germany and France at the municipal level. It is indicating for regulatory challenges in the federal planning system in Germany. The findings thus prompt a stronger debate of the specific configurations of land policies in the two countries and beyond. Especially on how land policies aim at promoting or regulating for a more sustainable built urban form through municipal actors and planning stakeholders.

Keywords: land policy evaluation, urban form, geo-data analysis

Contact:

Kleiner, Caspar

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Accessibility (US6B)

Estimating pedestrian volumes using data on land use, built environment, infrastructure characteristics, and count data from automated video analytics

GOLPAYEGANI, Elham; HANTSCH, Sebastian; MEDICUS, Matthias; GERIKE, Regine*

Many cities in Germany are highly engaged in promoting walking, but hardly any data on street-level pedestrian volumes exist. This lack of data hinders evidence-based planning, the formulation of measurable goals and their monitoring. The goal of this study is to develop a method for estimating pedestrian volumes based on openly accessible spatial data.

Pedestrian count data, the study's dependent variable, were collected using cameras installed on both sides of 56 street sections in 14 cities in Germany. The data were automatically processed using OpenTrafficCam (OTC), a tool to extract pedestrian volumes from video footage.

The independent variables were primarily sourced from open platforms such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Google Map's Street View. They include infrastructure data (e.g., sidewalk width, building characteristics), weather data (e.g., temperature, precipitation), demographic data (e.g., population density), and POIs (e.g., shops, educational institutions). Two types of POIs were considered: (1) the number and type of POIs located on each street section (On-street POIs), (2) Values based on the influence area of these POIs in generating pedestrian traffic (Buffer POIs). For the analysis of the Buffer POIs, POIs were categorized by type; each was assigned a unique sphere of influence and the degree of overlap with each street sections was calculated.

Given the count nature of the dependent variable, a negative binomial model was chosen. The counts were considered twofold: for the whole cross-section and each street side of the street section. The modeling followed a stepwise process, based on multiple model configurations, considering combinations of uncorrelated variables, using On-street and/or Buffer POIs. Finally, models were ranked based on their statistical performance and plausibility of the variables.

Before modelling, a correlation analysis of the independent variables was performed. Correlations indicate that Buffer POIs of different categories tend to emerge together, as if the presence of one encourages the presence of others along the nearby street sections. Also, Buffer POIs are significantly correlated with the architectural characteristics of its streetscape (e.g. average number of floors, number of different building colors, ratio of closed buildings to section length, and ratio of glass frontage to section length). In addition, streets with a high concentration of Buffer POIs are mainly located in the city center, reflecting the area's significance as a core location for multiple facilities.

As a result of the modeling process 24 best-performing models were selected (12 for entire street sections and 12 for individual street sides). The following insights could be derived: Pedestrian volumes tend to be higher on streets with wider pavements, taller buildings, and less speed for motorized vehicles, highlighting the critical role of key street characteristics in design and operation. Among all types of POIs, service, retail, and gastronomy venues are associated with higher pedestrian volumes than any other facility. Interestingly, sports facilities negatively impact pedestrian volumes, challenging the common assumption that all POIs contribute positively to pedestrian volumes.

Keywords: Pedestrian Volumes, land use, automated count data

Contact:

Golpayegani, Elham

Technische Universität Dresden

Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Accessibility (US6B)

Diagnosing Urban Maturation in Small and Medium Towns in Sri Lanka: A Spatial Framework Integrating Accessibility, Density, and Land Use Dynamics

*ABENAYAKE, Charithmali Chethika; JAYASINGHE, Amila**

Cities evolve through time. Time series analysis of the urban form, that maps the dynamics of urban morphological elements across chronological eras has been widely applied in demonstrating the evolutionary process of cities world-wide. It is logical to assume that the small urban centers gradually evolved into matured cities during this long-term process. In the global-north, a rapid and unprecedented urbanization was evident with the immediate effect of industrial revolution, i.e. a century ago. Whereas in the Global South, the rapid urbanization is a living reality, hence measuring the level of maturity or comprehending the maturation process is particularly important for shaping sustainable trajectories. This study introduces a composite spatial methodology to assess the urban maturation processes in rapidly urbanizing localities with referring to a set of small and medium towns in Sri Lanka. Drawing on the conceptual foundations of Natural Urban Maturation and network analysis, the research seeks to identify the spatial logic of the evolution of urban form and its implications on contemporary urban planning practices.

The proposed framework classifies urban areas along a continuum from fragmented sprawl to consolidated urban form. Three core spatial domains structure the analysis are Network Centrality, Built Density and Land Use Mix. The Spatial Maturity Index is composed of built form-normalized indicators including the integration of street network, road capacity, Floor Area Ratio (FAR), building height and land use entropy. The methodology was tested across ten Sri Lankan towns through GIS-based morphological analysis. Statistical correlation and spatial autocorrelation methods are applied to validate relationships and detect clustering of development patterns.

Findings revealed that early-stage towns tend to exhibit high integration levels leading to high accessibility yet low density and land use diversity, resulting in a state of 'incomplete urbanity'. Transitional towns also display spatial mismatch, where infrastructural investment precedes morphological consolidation—leading to inconsistent land use and risks such as inefficient land consumption. Whereas more-matured towns those have been historically-evolved demonstrate a highly compact built forms, and diversified land-use arrangement and highly connected street networks, reflecting a convergence toward a functionally integrated urban structure. Nonetheless there were no circumstances in the studied towns where diversified-land use mix or densified built forms resulted without high level of integration. Further the study examined how road capacity and network accessibility interact with urban density and land-use diversity, showing that enhanced accessibility often fuels incoherent or low-density growth when not guided by supportive land policy, and adequate infrastructure supply.

The study developed a decision-support tool to model the interdependencies among land use, accessibility, and urban densities—offering critical insights for managing development in emerging urban regions. This research offers a replicable, data-driven methodology for diagnosing spatial transformations in non-metropolitan settings. It contributes to the Planning practice and Policy by introducing a robust, interdisciplinary framework for evaluating the spatial dynamics of urbanization.

Keywords: Urban Structure, Urban Maturation, Land Use, Land Use Planning and Policy, Spatial Data

Contact:

Abenayake, Charithmali Chethika

TUD, Dresden University of Technology
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Accessibility (US6B)

Quantifying Accessibility for Sustainable Urban Mobility Transitions

MIOTTI, Marco; HELLWEG, Stefanie*

The concept of “accessibility” encompasses three key drivers of urban mobility patterns and therefore mobility energy use: people (who is traveling?), places (where do people want to go to?), and the mobility infrastructure (how can they get there?). As such, accessibility metrics play an important role in many urban and land use planning applications. This includes efforts to design and develop urban areas for more sustainable mobility without sacrificing the quality of service that those mobility systems provide. Such accessibility metrics range from simple counts (such as the number of supermarkets within a 500m radius) to far more complex options based on gravity decay functions or so-called ‘logsum’ appraisals. While there are inherent trade-offs between how powerful, intuitive, and context-specific different accessibility metrics are, systematic comparisons have been rare. In this work, we evaluate how well simple accessibility metrics perform compared to complex ones that require more data and that are more difficult to interpret. Based on these observations, we investigate what these metrics can tell us about how to design more sustainable urban systems that maintain or even improve the levels of accessibility. We evaluate accessibility metrics of different complexities and based on travel distance, travel time, and generalized travel cost (utility) by how well they correlate with mobility greenhouse gas emissions—an indicator that reflects both modal choices and the typical daily distance covered with those modes. We do so for different types of trips: work, education, groceries, other errands, and leisure. We find that easily interpretable accessibility metrics perform 80-90% as well as more complex ones. However, the meaningfulness of any accessibility metrics heavily depends on correctly specified hyperparameters, and the ideal parameters can depend on the trip purpose and the type of travel costs (distance, time, or utility) used. We also highlight that accessibility operates at different scales: the local scale (< 500 m) is important to accurately capturing active mobility (walking and cycling) trips, while the general urban scale is important to capture the impact of sprawl on typical trip distances for motorized travel. Based on these observations, we identify specific urban planning levers that may lead to changes in mobility behavior and promote more sustainable mobility.

Keywords: Accessibility, Urban form, Metrics, Sustainable Mobility

Contact:

Miotti, Marco
ETH Zürich
Switzerland

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Accessibility (US6B)

An Objective Walkability Assessment of Canakkale City Center for Enhancing Pedestrian Environments

TURKEN, Araf Oyku; HAMAMCIOGLU, Cenk*

Walking is the most common mode of transport that enhances well-being and livability in cities and has been promoted by European planning authorities via Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMP) to reduce car dependency and foster accessible neighborhoods. In Turkey, the development of SUMPs has recently gained momentum, with the completion of one plan yet. However, many cities, including Canakkale, have not established SUMPs, resulting in urbanized areas lacking active transportation options. Despite strategic recognition, many mid and small-sized cities struggle to implement walking-oriented interventions due to institutional limitations, which results in inadequate human-friendly streets and pedestrian safety concerns. As one of the representatives of this, Canakkale was selected as a pilot case study based on its non-metropolitan character, population, urban land coverage, landscape and street variations, diversity of pedestrianization, and speed regulation practices.

The objective of this study is twofold: developing an objective walkability assessment framework and defining walking-related problem typologies in the built environment to serve as a guide for the walkability phase of SUMP processes and pedestrian-friendly interventions in the future. With this aim, this research adopts a multi-method approach to score objective walkability in seven neighborhoods in the Canakkale city center. By focusing on parameters such as land use, accessibility, street network, pedestrian comfort, safety, and street design, AHP procedures were employed with urban design professionals to formulate a hierarchical framework. GIS and space syntax analyses assessed land use diversity, density, accessibility, slope, and street networks. Fieldwork was conducted to document streetscape features via an online mapping tool. The final stage of the research involved the calculation of overall walkability scores for each street, with these scores being based on built-environmental elements using municipal and collected data.

The preliminary findings indicate inequalities in spatial walkability scores across neighborhoods due to sub-parameters. Safety-related issues in zones with high concentrations of derelict buildings, neighborhood characteristics based on land-use diversity, accessibility to points of interest and public facilities, and street connectivity play a critical role in these disparities. Additionally, the presence of public spaces and the quality of urban design elements and street furniture significantly influence spatial aesthetic scores. The research concludes by identifying typologies of walkability issues through a comparative analysis of neighborhoods in the city center of Canakkale. Thus, this study is envisioned to support urban planners and policymakers in reforming future action strategies for SUMPs and to provide an analytical base for developing pedestrian-friendly micro-interventions.

Keywords: walkability, pedestrian movement, GIS, accessibility, space-syntax

Contact:

Turken, Araf Oyku

Yildiz Technical University

Turkiye

Track: Urban Structure and Policy

Urban Structure and Policy: Housing (US7A)

Quantifying segregation: A spatial-statistical study of internal migrants' residential choices in Hyderabad

*PUTTA, Vanitha; BISWAS, Arindam**

Urbanization and internal migration are interlinked and shaped by historical, economic, and administrative factors in India. Internal migration in India has emerged as a significant driver of demographic, spatial, and socio-economic transformation in urban centres. The city of Hyderabad, a major metropolitan hub in southern India, has witnessed a consistent influx of internal migrants over recent decades. Hyderabad is the capital of the state of Telangana in India. These migrants, varying widely in terms of their socio-economic backgrounds, regions of origin, and migration motivations, engage with the city in spatially uneven ways. Their residential choices—whether voluntary or constrained—reflect broader structural dynamics, local housing market configurations, and often, invisible forms of social exclusion. In urban India, residential segregation is prominently shaped by caste-based discrimination, socioeconomic disparities, and state-led planning practices that systematically marginalize certain groups. The aim of this paper is to investigate the spatial residential segregation and quantify the degree of segregation experienced by internal migrants in Hyderabad using a combination of spatial and statistical methodologies.

The research adopts a mixed-methods approach that integrates spatial analysis, quantitative data, and statistical tools. The empirical data includes primary data collected through fieldwork conducted in three wards in GHMC (Greater Hyderabad Municipal Corporation) that house significant migrant populations. GHMC is the biggest Municipal Corporation of Hyderabad. The study uses household-level data to extract key indicators such as migrant status, income and education level, occupation type, duration of stay, housing typology, residential preferences, etc., and spatial data to extract the residential typologies. At the spatial level, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are employed to map the distribution of residential typologies. A total of 10 distinct residential typologies were identified based on built form, affordability, and resident composition. Each typology exhibits different levels of spatial integration and access to infrastructure. Informal settlements and peripheral colonies are most marked by segregation, both in terms of migrant concentration and infrastructural deficit, reinforcing a double marginalization—social and spatial.

For spatial analysis of residential segregation, Massey and Denton's (1988) framework is applied to examine key dimensions such as evenness, exposure, clustering, and concentration. To delve deeper into the factors influencing housing preferences, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted. These findings were then validated using ANOVA to detect significant differences in housing preference across income groups. A significant statistical relationship is observed between the income level and the type of residential typology migrants prefer.

In conclusion, the research finds that internal migrants in Hyderabad experience varying levels of residential segregation shaped by socio-economic factors such as income, marital status, occupation, family size, safety, etc. The spatial-statistical approach employed here underscores the layered complexity of migrant urbanism, where migrants make active choices about where to live, and these choices are reflections of structural constraints.

Keywords: spatial segregation, residential segregation, residential choices, residential typologies, internal migrant

Contact:

Putta, Vanitha
IIT ROORKEE
India

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Housing (US7A)

Assessing Densification Potential through Spatial Comparison of Planned vs. Actual Land Use in Hamburg

HERNANDEZ, Juan; DALLY, Benjamin; REISWICH, Nicole; NOENNIG, Jörg*

Densification (Nachverdichtung) is a key urban strategy aimed at accommodating development needs while limiting the consumption of undeveloped land. By concentrating housing and services within existing urban areas, cities can reduce infrastructure costs, minimize travel distances, retain tax revenue, and strengthen social cohesion. Among the various approaches to densification, one crucial distinction is between developments that occur within existing legal planning constraints and those requiring changes to zoning regulations. The presented work focuses on the former.

In collaboration with a municipal land development agency (as practice partner), the authors, as a research institution, are developing the AGORA tool (Analytics for Ground Property and Real Estate Assessment). The tool supports strategic land management by identifying parcels in Hamburg that exhibit underused development capacity within the constraints of existing planning regulations.

To assess such densification potential, the project compares actual land use data from the ALKIS cadastral system with regulatory data from the XPlanung standard. As a first analytical step, the focus is on the Grundflächenzahl (GRZ), a planning parameter indicating the allowable ratio of building footprint to land area. A core challenge lies in aligning buildings to parcels and assigning parcels to planning areas with defined GRZ values. The method addresses these spatial mismatches and calculates build-out intensity on a parcel level. Now in its third iteration, the comparison method is being tested within LIG and integrated into internal workflows of the AGORA tool. This case study demonstrates how available geodata can be used to evaluate densification potential within existing legal limits, providing a transferable model for data-informed urban land policy and sustainable development planning.

In this talk, we present the methodological foundation of the comparison algorithm and its iterative development, shaped by the motivations of the involved partners and computational limitations associated to the data structure and the tools used. We share as well, the current results of the implementation, in relation to the user test done with our partner.

Keywords: Nachverdichtung, Densification, ALKIS, XPlanung, Land use comparison, Parcel-level analysis

Contact:

Hernandez, Juan
HafenCity Universität Hamburg
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Urban Structure and Policy: Housing (US7A)

Evaluating the Impact of Housing and Neighbourhood Characteristics on Housing Vacancy : Insights for targeting urban interventions

*FLAS, Mathilde**; *TELLER, Jacques*; *COOLS, Mario*

Housing vacancy is a complex and context-specific phenomenon, with significant implications for land use efficiency. In Western European countries, the reasons for vacancy are often explained by the owners' behaviour. Yet, we hypothesize that owners' decisions are influenced by the attractiveness of their property on the market and that the characteristics of housing vacancy may provide insight into fine-scale market dynamics. Most previous research on vacant housing characteristics has used data aggregated at the level of neighbourhoods, cities or regions. There has been few research based on parcel data and - to our knowledge - none for Western Europe, probably due to the lack of data.

This study combines water and electricity consumption data with field verification to identify vacant single-family housing and examine their characteristics. The Liège agglomeration was chosen as a case study due to its complex urban dynamics, including shrinkage due to industrial decline, suburbanization, and the increasing commodification of housing – trends that are widespread in Western Europe since World War II and that influences the housing market.

Logistic regression models were used to analyze the factors influencing housing vacancy, comparing variables related to the neighborhood (e.g., socioeconomic precarity, age distribution, changes in the number of housing units) and housing characteristics (e.g., property age, presence of a garage, cadastral income). Our analysis reveals distinct trends: areas with higher vacancy rates are characterized by substandard, low-value housing, while low vacancy areas show vacancy patterns related to personal convenience and comfort preferences. In both cases, factors at the housing level have more influence than the factors at the neighborhood level.

A simplified model, using only land and building register data, was then applied to all single-family housing parcels in the Liège agglomeration to identify the least attractive housing whose characteristics make them prone to vacancy. Hotspot analysis using the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic highlights concentration of vacant-prone housing and enables us to identify some patterns (enclosed areas, dead-end streets, old et narrow streets in village centres, etc.).

While actions to tackle vacancy are generally taken on a case-by-case basis and are very time-consuming, this study lays the foundations for thinking about urban strategies at the neighbourhood or street level, such as de-densification or street-wide renovation. By targeting housing that is prone to vacancy, this approach also addresses related issues, such as managing substandard housing and improving the overall attractiveness of urban spaces.

Keywords: housing vacancy characteristics, vacancy parcel data, consumption data, vacancy risk

Contact:

Flas, Mathilde
University of Liège
Belgium

Track: *Digital Twins and Decision Making*
Urban Structure and Policy: *Housing (US7A)*

A collection of building changes data to clarify densification concepts

BUCHER, Bénédicte; SONG, Yibo*

Could maps help our societies discuss land changes the same way topographic maps have been adopted for ages to locate entities and discuss routes? If such maps exist, could they improve our individual and collective capacities to understand what desirable densification is and how to make it happen? The stakes of densification call for more comparative studies, multidisciplinary research, more trust between public and private sectors, and more democratic debate. Current maps to discuss densification are grounded on indicators and abstract areas. Not everyone can interpret them. Their granularity is often too coarse to account for local variations in the contrasting impacts of denser urban environments.

This motivates our research. We study the production of a new kind of maps fitted to open discussions on densification. Buildings and how they change over time are good candidates to put on such maps. They are commonsense entities. Overlaying them with context like green field, street network, public transports help observing the increase of habitat in built-up areas, the saving or consumption of green fields, the development of new infrastructures, the development of low-quality housing programs with insufficient amenities. A model has been proposed to derive automatically maps of building changes on city regions using different topographic buildings surveys available on the past decades in Germany, the UK and France. These initial maps are further used to refine the highly generic Building Change model, which was limited to changes that could be detected between topographic features, identify ambiguous words and implicit hypotheses.

This clarification of shared words to discuss about building changes is grounded on a collaborative, multi-lingual and multi-perspective collection of building changes data, that embraces different context, Germany, the UK and France, which timespan is included in the past decades. Items can be either a change of a specific entity, or a change of a neighbour, or a change occurring at the level of the urban sprawl. Each item is associated with data (buildings surveys differentials, digital elevation models, properties, aerial imagery), visuals that can be displayed on a screen, and narratives. Narratives are acquired from local portals where municipalities describe their development projects and from sessions where the collection is presented to experts who comment on visuals and relate them to densification. The collection is produced manually using data that are produced automatically like differentials of vector data or differentials of digital elevation models.

A key aspect we explain more in details is to attach context to building changes items and to narratives. This is crucial for our capacity to generalise concepts and identify ambiguities. It is achieved by a formal model to store the provenance of items on the one hand and the provenance of narratives on the other hand. The provenance of an item is a full description of how the item was produced, including how the focus area was selected. The provenance of a narrative includes the state of the collection that was presented during the session and the order in which items were presented.

Keywords: Building changes, vector data, maps, densification

Contact:

Bucher, Bénédicte
Université Gustave Eiffel, IGN-ENSG, LASTIG
France

*Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)*

Becoming asset managers under institutional uncertainty: local land governance in Ukraine

ANISIMOV, Oleksandr; VAKHNIAK, Liliia; BUITELAAR, Edwin*

Much research about local land governance is currently focused on understanding the drivers of local land policies, their effectiveness and priorities, chiefly in light of the housing, climate and energy crises. However, we know little about how local governments start building capacity as well as develop policy directions, setting future path dependencies in land use systems.

With a newly acquired land management and spatial planning autonomy as a result of the land and administrative reforms in 2019-2021, Ukrainian municipalities are now the key political bodies responsible for land use. Lacking previous experience, they are trying to find their own way of governing lands in the context of the war.

In this paper, we explore organisational learning in the use of public land (land portfolio management) and control over privately owned lands (land use management). By doing so, this paper addresses the question of how municipalities develop land management policies, lock in certain modalities and invent new ones. Building on interviews and questionnaires, we construct an understanding of the emerging local land governance regime with a view to enhancing and supporting sustainable local land policy and land management practice in Ukraine. Findings on institutional learning in municipalities would also inform future comparative analysis and support further research venues across Europe and beyond.

Keywords: land use, local governments, land policy, organizational learning

Contact:

Anisimov, Oleksandr
Aalto University
Finland

*Track: Digital Twins and Decision Making
Poster Session (P1)*

The role of data quality for the data- driven prediction of building age with machine learning

TEICHMANN, Sophie; HEROLD, Hendrik; HECHT, Robert*

The building age is an important indicator for sustainability planning, for example when it comes to retrofitting potential or risk assessment. The EUBUCCO project compiled all available building stock data with building ages, building types (residential or non-residential), building heights and footprints across Europe in 2021. The project revealed that data availability and definitions differ greatly between states and regions.

In this study, we evaluate the required data quality to predict building ages based on morphological features using Switzerland and Germany as case studies. According to ISO 19157:2013, data quality comprises four elements: completeness, thematic accuracy, logical consistency, temporal quality. We investigate the effects of data completeness and thematic accuracy (referring mainly to the building age). Switzerland provides a dataset with nationwide coverage and detailed building age entries (up to the month). Germany does not provide a

joint dataset. Only few federal states provide an open dataset with the building age.

After preprocessing the data and deriving the relevant features such as proximity to the next building or building height, this work applies the same machine learning approaches to predict the building age. The algorithms used are gradient boosting and graph neural networks. Both algorithms are known for their ability to handle spatial data. A separate machine learning model is fitted to the available data for each of the countries. To ensure comparability, the same amount of hyperparameter optimization is performed. Comparing the two set-ups provides insight into how quality affects the prediction. The results can inform further model development and potentially influence policies for effectively sharing building age data.

Keywords: building age, machine learning, spatial data, data quality

Contact:

Teichmann, Sophie
TU Dresden
Germany

Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)

Missing links – How much land is legally secured for biotope networks in Germany?

HABERMANN, Johannes Tobias; BLEYHL, Benjamin*

Biotope networks aim to connect fragmented habitats – such as forests, meadows, rivers and wetlands – by creating corridors or stepping stones that support biodiversity, ecological resilience and exchange. These networks play a crucial role in meeting legal obligations set out in instruments such as Article 10 of the EU Fauna-Flora-Habitat Directive and Article 4 of Nature Restoration Law for the connectivity of habitats. In Germany, the federal states are mandated to designate 10 percent of their land area for biotope networks. In response, the federal states have identified large-scale areas deemed ecologically suitable.

However, biotope networks can only fulfil their intended purpose if they are legally secured. As early as 2017, the German legislator emphasized that the biggest deficit in the implementation of the biotope network is its legal securement. In Germany, legal securement can take the form of nature conservation sites, land-use plans, contractual agreements, or land ownership (§ 20 sect. 2 Federal Law on Nature Conservation). Among these, land ownership by public authorities offers a higher effectiveness for nature restoration measures, whereas voluntary cooperation between landowners and the public sector increases acceptance of measures. Yet, the spatial distribution of biotope networks and their legal securement has so far not been assessed across Germany.

This research, funded by the German Federal Agency for Nature Conservation, assesses the extent of legally secured areas designated for biotope networks. We seek to understand the function of both regulatory and cooperative instruments in achieving robust land securement. In a first step, we developed a consistent framework to assess the legal status of areas within biotope networks and collected spatial data from state authorities and large-scale landholders engaged in conservation—such as land agencies, NGOs, and foundations. Second, we compare the legally secured areas to state-level concepts and policy objectives. The results will be discussed with public and civil society stakeholders to identify implementation deficits and develop policy recommendations.

Keywords: habitat fragmentation, landscape permeability, land securement

Contact:

Habermann, Johannes Tobias
Bosch & Partner GmbH
Germany

Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)

Multitemporal Local Climate Zone Classification across European Cities

HELLINGS, Anna; RIENOW, Andreas; BECHTEL, Benjamin; DEMUZERE, Matthias*

Urban expansion changes local climate conditions through modifications in surface properties and energy balance. We developed a multitemporal Local Climate Zone mapping approach to systematically track land use transformations across European cities from 2000 to 2023. Local Climate Zones represent a standardized classification system that categorizes urban and natural landscapes based on their thermal, radiative, and morphological properties, providing a framework for understanding climate impacts of different urban forms. Our methodology combines neural networks with change detection algorithms to monitor seventeen Local Climate Zone categories. Deep learning models incorporate batch normalization and dropout to classify urban morphology based on building structure, surface cover, and vegetation patterns. Feature importance analysis using separate models provides insights into the most discriminative characteristics for Local Climate Zone differentiation. We apply Multivariate Alteration Detection to identify significant land use transitions between time periods.

The analysis relies on Landsat imagery processed through cloud masking and temporal compositing using percentile reducers on the CODE-DE platform. Additional input features include elevation data from Copernicus Digital Elevation Model to capture topographic influences on urban climate zones. Training areas combine manually digitized zones with existing WUDAPT (World Urban Database and Access Portal Tools) datasets, validated using building height information from global settlement layers. This approach ensures representative coverage of Local Climate Zone types across different European urban contexts.

Several technical challenges required careful consideration. Harmonizing data across different Landsat sensors while maintaining temporal consistency proved critical for multidecadal analysis. We implemented spatial cross-validation to address autocorrelation effects in training data. Class-specific Gaussian filtering improved spatial coherence while preserving important urban boundaries. The processing workflow incorporates spectral indices and morphological features to capture the diverse characteristics of European urban environments.

Change detection employs iteratively reweighted Multivariate Alteration Detection to generate probability maps of land use transitions. This approach quantifies conversion from natural and agricultural areas to various built-up zone types, particularly around urban peripheries where development pressure is highest. The resulting continental-scale dataset will enable detailed investigation of how building density and height variations within different Local Climate Zone types influence urban heat development. Urban planners will benefit from data-driven insights about optimal building arrangements for heat mitigation, while policy makers receive quantitative evidence for climate-sensitive development strategies. This comprehensive monitoring across all European cities supports comparative analysis of urban development patterns and their thermal impacts, contributing to more effective climate-informed planning throughout Europe.

Keywords: Local Climate Zones, Land Use Change, Multitemporal Analysis, Deep Learning, European Cities

Contact:

Hellings, Anna

BBSR, Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development
Germany

Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)

Fostering Ecological Considerations in Urban Planning by Employing a Multidisciplinary Approach

*PUNDSACK, Meret**

Urbanization is associated with increased sealing, habitat fragmentation, rising temperatures, and anthropogenic noise in densely built-up areas. Since these impacts are linked to the deterioration of human health as well as biodiversity loss, new solutions need to be found to make cities more livable and resilient.

Various urban planning approaches already exist to account for and mitigate these impacts by transforming urban structures while recognizing the value of nature beyond its ornamental purpose. However, such approaches often focus on isolated aspects and prioritize selected disciplines over others. For example, Nature-based Solutions are not always considered in planning decisions, and the concept of ecosystem services itself is often applied in a narrow sense, e.g., when specific trees are selected for cooling effects while their broader ecological role, including benefits for wildlife, is neglected.

In this way, urban planning is not yet a multidisciplinary, integral process, but rather a mosaic of multiple different disciplines whose coordination is often only attempted afterward. This later harmonization often fails because individual disciplinary solutions are not compatible. In particular, human-centric approaches such as traffic planning often lead to compromises at the expense of nature available for humans and other organisms. In contrast, early data-driven integration of multiple disciplines can uncover synergies between the different disciplines. Meanwhile, multidisciplinary, collaborative, and participatory approaches have proven effective in delivering resilient solutions and have already been applied to the urban environment.

In this paper, we advocate for the early integration and equal importance attribution to multiple planning perspectives into a single, holistic approach. We point out the conceptual, but also technical challenges that have to be overcome for interdisciplinary integration, in particular with respect to the further development of disciplinary models. We argue that integration can best be achieved when disciplines come together by jointly developing urban planning scenarios. This will also facilitate the identification of interfaces between disciplines with respect to data formats and modelled variables. We also argue that such scenario development should include stakeholders in a co-creative approach to make sure that scenarios will address real-world planning questions and challenges.

We illustrate how integration could proceed by considering the integration of a traffic planning and an ecological connectivity model based on multiple scenarios, to highlight the interactions between both disciplines and the benefits that accrue from early integration in the planning process. To illustrate how the co-creative process can be conducted, we report on early steps of the CoCoNet-project (Co-creative Cohabitation Network), which aims to develop an integrated, multidisciplinary, and participatory modeling-based planning approach further integrating microclimate and noise models. By pointing out both the advantages of multidisciplinary integrations as well as suggesting a pathway on how this can be achieved, this paper aims to encourage planners from different disciplines to collaborate in the development of desirable urban planning pathways while considering the needs of humans and urban wildlife.

Keywords: Urban ecology, Multidisciplinary, Urban ecological modeling

Contact:

Pundsack, Meret
TU München
Germany

Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)

AI-based Enrichment of Building Data by Predicting Demographic Data

RAFIEI, Fatemeh; HECHT, Robert; BLANCO-VOGT, Angela*

Accurate demographic predictions at fine spatial resolution play a critical role in helping urban planners allocate resources efficiently, ensuring better housing, transportation, and services for diverse populations. Traditional data collection methods, such as censuses and surveys, suffer from limitations in frequency, spatial resolution, and cost, which make it difficult to capture dynamic demographic changes in urban areas. This research proposes a solution to address this gap by leveraging machine learning (ML) models to enrich building data with predicted demographic characteristics at the building level. The primary aim of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness and adaptability of machine learning models, specifically Random Forest (RF) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), for predicting demographic patterns, including population count and age group proportions, in the German context.

The study uses Stuttgart, known as an economic hub with a strong industrial presence and a mixture of industrial and modern urban developments, as the training area. Dresden, a historical city with a mix of heritage and modern developments, is used as the test area to examine the generalizability of the models across cities with contrasting urban forms. The dataset includes detailed two-dimensional building attributes derived from 3D CityGML data, 100-meter grid census data, OpenStreetMap points of interest (POI), block data, house coordinate data, and accessibility measures. Through extensive feature engineering, over 50 predictive indicators were generated. These indicators fall into two main categories: building-level attributes (e.g., area, height, volume, shape complexity measured by Equivalent Rectangular Index (ERI) and Proximity Index (PI)) and urban-level indicators (e.g., walking distance or time to the city center, built-up density, number of neighboring buildings, and accessibility to various POI types within a 15-minute walk).

A key challenge in this research was the disaggregation of demographic data from the grid level to individual buildings, which significantly influenced the model outcomes. Despite these challenges, the results demonstrate that population prediction achieved good accuracy using the RF model, showing that building-level data combined with ML can effectively estimate population distribution. However, the prediction of age-related demographics was less precise, primarily due to inaccuracies and limitations in the input datasets. The analysis also revealed that POI data had an impact on age-group predictions but played a less critical role in population estimation.

This research highlights the potential of integrating AI with urban data as an alternative or complement to traditional demographic data collection methods. It demonstrates the critical importance of high-quality, detailed building data and carefully designed feature engineering for achieving accurate demographic predictions. Future work should focus on refining model hyperparameters and incorporating more accurate building-level demographic data. Addressing these challenges is essential for enhancing the generalizability of the approach and ensuring its applicability across diverse urban environments.

Keywords: Machine learning, Random Forest, EXtreme Gradient Boosting, Demographic prediction, Building data enrichment

Contact:

Rafiei, Fatemeh

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IÖR)
Germany

*Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)*

Urban Activity Patterns and Transit-Oriented Dynamics: Mapping Geo-Tagged Venue Data in Istanbul

*SOYGÜZELOĞLU, Burcu**

Urban transport nodes such as rail stations are vital enablers of mobility and accessibility in metropolitan regions. Understanding the dynamic spatial patterns of activity around these hubs is increasingly crucial for guiding equitable and sustainable urban development. This study explores the urban spatial dynamics surrounding the Marmaray mass transit stations on the Anatolian side of Istanbul, which employs venue-based data from the location-based social network, Foursquare. By analyzing venue distributions within a 500-meter radius of 29 stations using Kernel Density Estimation and K-means clustering, four distinct clusters of stations were identified, each characterized by different configurations of retail, dining, recreation, and service-oriented functions. The findings highlight significant variation in activity density and functional mix across the corridor, which reveals spatial inequalities and differentiated urban roles of transit-adjacent areas. By integrating geo-tagged data, this research contributes to the growing body of work on data-informed urban analysis and offers actionable insights for transit-oriented development and urban policy.

Keywords: geo-tagged venue data, Istanbul, spatial dynamics, transit-oriented development, urban activity patterns

Contact:

Soyguzeloglu, Burcu
Gebze Technical University
Turkiye

Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)

Endogenous dynamics of urban expansion

MARQUIS, Ulysse Pierre; ARTIME, Oriol; GALLOTTI, Riccardo; BARTHELEMY, Marc

Dynamics of urban growth have been extensively studied from the demographic and economic perspective. However, little is known about urban spatial expansion, despite its crucial environmental, social and economic implications. Recent modeling efforts, based on various approaches such as reaction-diffusion equations, cluster growth or percolation, lack robust empirical grounding due to i) improper definition of city delimitations, ii) difficulty of choosing an appropriate time parameter and iii) little data availability. Remote sensing techniques have made available new urban artificial land use datasets, at a yearly frequency and fine-grained spatial resolution, such as the World Settlement Footprint Evolution dataset. Combining this dataset and historical population records, we propose a surface growth framework for the analysis of urban sprawl. We focus on the largest connected component of urban fabric and study its radial growth. We focused on 19 major cities spanning 3 continents between 1985 and 2015. We analyze the growth speed of the urban area in function of population and find generally linear scaling, resonating with recent Lemoy and Caruso cross-sectional findings. Moreover, we quantify deviations to isotropic growth through scaling of directional growth. Through the measure of the largest aggregated cluster, we can measure whether the growth of urban fabric resembles diffusion or aggregation processes. We notice a striking relation between demographic pressure and large cluster coalescence. Finally, we apply techniques from surface growth physics on the urban fringe. Surface growth theory has been developed in the last decades and has been applied to a variety of physical processes, such as molecular-beam epitaxy or tumor growth. Types of interfaces growth are classified in universality classes, a finite set of exponents characterizing the interface, both statically and dynamically. In this work, using recent radial surface growth techniques, we were able to measure the local roughness exponent, the growth exponent and the correlation length exponent. We identified an unique value for the local roughness exponent while the other exponents vary across cities. This work is, up to the authors knowledge, the first longitudinal analysis of the dynamics of urban sprawl and provide new empirical findings, necessary for modeling and simulating urban sprawl.

Keywords: Urban sprawl, scaling, suburbanization, land use, surface growth

Contact:

Marquis, Ulysse Pierre
Fondazione Bruno Kessler
France

*Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)*

The Research Data Centre at Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development

NIESWAND, Maria

The IOER RDC (IÖR-FDZ) offers cross-scale and cross-sectional, high-resolution object and spatial data sets, indicators, models, simulations and digital tools on the topics of land use, landscape quality, settlements, buildings, ecosystem services, urban greenery and environmental risks.

Our services address stakeholders from research, politics and administration, the media, business and civil society. They are further developed and made available in an application- and user-orientated manner in order to address the various needs of the user groups and increase the usability of the data.

In order to achieve this effectively, the IOER RDC (IÖR-FDZ) pursues a modular approach: data and technical functionalities (so-called components) are developed in such a way that they can be combined and used flexibly in different contexts, both internally and externally.

The poster or short presentation will illustrate this modular approach and present new data offerings. In addition, the poster/ presentation provides an overview of newly developed options for accessing, linking and (re)using IOER data.

Keywords: research infrastructure, geospatial, FAIR data

Contact:

Nieswand, Maria

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

*Track: Submission for Posters
Poster Session (P1)*

Mapping the long-term evolution of land use on a national scale - the case of Germany

HEROLD, Hendrik; HARTMANN, André; KISS, Estzer

Many Earth science disciplines rely on long-term time series data. Historic land use is a valuable information source and proxy for various applications in biodiversity science, climate protection, urban analytics and many more. However, the acquisition of this data is not trivial and on a national scale extremely labour-intensive. In this study, we investigate the feasibility and possibilities of extracting this information automatically from its historical sources. We present results in terms of both the temporal data source availability and methodical approaches for a national application.

Keywords: land use, historical maps, long-term evolution, national level

Contact:

Herold, Hendrik

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Poster Session (P1)

Do large housing estates correspond to the 15-minute city? A co-creative and data-driven assessment approach applied to five case studies

PETRY, Lisanne, HECHT, Robert*, MAZUMDER, Srijan, PAJARES, Elias, KAMOUN, Cyrine, HÄNCHEN, Linda, RÖSSLER, Stefanie

The concept of the 15-minute city has gained considerable attention in recent years as a promising solution for promoting sustainable mobility and improving residents' quality of life. The idea is to provide residents with easy access to important services and facilities within 15 minutes on foot or by bike. Different types of urban neighbourhoods, in terms of spatial density, infrastructure provision or requirements and opportunities of local people, might have different pre-conditions and needs to apply the concept. Large housing estates (LHEs) on the one hand are often planned as compact, people centred neighbourhoods, providing all facilities for daily needs. On the other hand, in recent years they followed different trajectories, causing several challenges, as limited and ageing infrastructure, changing socio-demographic situation and limited public awareness.

This study investigates the suitability of existing methods for assessing 15-minute city maturity for application to LHEs. The gravity-based approach to assessing accessibility to basic essentials (in the areas of health, education, recreation, commerce etc.) is applied to European LHE case studies, using a combination of official municipal data, OpenStreetMap data, and data from participatory, co-creative approaches. The results show that the complex challenges and limitations of implementing the 15-minute city concept in LHEs must be carefully considered.

One of the main limitations of the study is the use of gravity-based indicators, which are difficult to interpret and may not accurately reflect user needs and preferences. Additionally, the weighting of indicators in the calculation of the 15-minute score may need to be adjusted to take into account regional and user-specific preferences. For example, the willingness to walk or cycle can vary significantly between different cities and regions. The study also highlights the importance of multimodal considerations, including public transport, walking, and cycling, for convenient and efficient access to essential services and facilities. Furthermore, the concept of walkability and cycleability is crucial for assessing urban environments, as it takes into account the safety, comfort, and attractiveness of walking and cycling routes. Moreover, the study raises questions about how the issue of work and employment can be addressed in the context of the 15-minute city concept. While the concept focuses on the accessibility of essential services and facilities, it is unclear how the needs of commuters and workers who may have to travel longer distances to their workplaces can be taken into account. This highlights the need for a more nuanced understanding of the complex links between transport, land use, and employment, as well as the development of more effective strategies to promote sustainable mobility and reduce the need for long commutes.

The study is part of the 15minESTATES research project, which aims to co-create spatial strategies for just and sustainable mobility in large-scale housing estates by investigating the spatial conditions and mobility needs of different social groups in these areas.

In summary, this study contributes to the growing body of research on the 15-minute city concept and highlights the need for differentiated and context-specific approaches to assessing and implementing sustainable mobility solutions in LHEs.

Keywords: 15-minute City, Large Housing Estate, Accessibility, Co-Creative

Contact:

Petry, Lisanne

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Poster Session (P1)

Colouring Cities: A Global Network and Open Platform for Collaborative Mapping of Building Stocks

HUDSON, Polly, CHUYKOV, Sergey, DANKE, Tabea, HAWAS, Allan, HAWAS, Oriol, HECHT, Robert, HEROLD, Hendrik, LARIMIAN, Taimaz, PALAIOLOGOU, Falli*

The Colouring Cities Research Programme (CCRP) is a global initiative designed to advance the collaborative mapping of national building stocks through an extensive network of interoperable platforms. Focused on facilitating progress toward the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), CCRP leverages open data methodologies, engaging a broad consortium of over 100 researchers from more than 30 nations. Experts from diverse fields—including computer science, data science, urban science, and environmental science—convene regional hubs across North America, Europe, the Middle East, Latin America, Africa, and the Asia Pacific. This multidisciplinary approach enhances cross-sector knowledge sharing, fostering a rich collaborative environment aimed at sustainable urban development.

CCRP utilizes open-source platforms that standardize data interfaces, allowing for the effective pooling and sharing of micro-spatial data. Through an innovative integration of crowdsourced, bulk, and streamed data, the program employs artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques to develop large-scale datasets, which are carefully moderated by academic experts to ensure accuracy. Subsequent crowd-verification processes further enrich these datasets, promoting the principles of openness, transparency, and democratic decision-making within the program. By emphasizing societal engagement, CCRP seeks to involve diverse stakeholders in the data collection and visualization processes, aligning academic research with community needs and sustainability objectives.

The platforms developed under CCRP provide an interactive map interface enabling collaborative data collection and visualization. With over 150 standardized spatial data classes, the platform categorizes data into 12 main areas, alongside bespoke data tailored to specific community needs. Ethical oversight remains a paramount concern within CCRP, as academic supervision governs the ethical collection of data, ensuring user privacy and preventing the publication of personal data. Multiple data capture methods enhance accessibility, allowing citizens to participate as "scientists" in the mapping initiative. Bulk uploads, API streaming, and computationally inferred data contribute to the robustness of the datasets gathered.

Moreover, all CCRP resources—including code, datasets, and methodologies—are made openly accessible under liberal licenses, reinforcing the ethos of transparency and facilitating widespread collaboration across diverse contexts. This commitment to open access ensures that community members, researchers, and policymakers can engage with and leverage the data effectively for local and global development goals.

Participation in the CCRP is possible at various levels and across different areas of expertise. Interested individuals and organizations can explore the available platforms online. At the local level, individuals are encouraged to support Colouring Cities initiatives by participating in various citizen science formats, thereby involving the community in mapping and sustainable development.

The CCRP offers a transformative framework for the collaborative mapping of urban environments, aspiring to catalyze significant advancements in sustainable development through integrative, ethical, and inclusive practices. By leveraging the strengths of a diverse global network, CCRP seeks to create invaluable resources for cities worldwide, thereby contributing to a more sustainable future for urban living.

Keywords: Participatory mapping, platform, machine learning, buildings, open source, open data, CCRP

Contact:

Hecht, Robert

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

Track: Urban Structure and Policy
Poster Session (P1)

Understanding the Interlinkages between Urban Sprawl, Landscape Fragmentation and Habitat Network Connectivity through a Resource Nexus Perspective

SESAY, Sampha, BEHNISCH, Martin, COETZEE, Serena*

Urban sprawl, landscape fragmentation, and habitat network connectivity have long been recognized as interrelated processes that pose significant challenges to sustainable land-use management, particularly in rapidly urbanizing regions. Globally, accelerated urban expansion has transformed natural landscapes, leading to habitat loss, landscape fragmentation, and increased competition for environmental resources. In West Africa, unregulated urban growth, deforestation, and infrastructure development have further amplified these transformations. However, previous studies have often examined these processes in isolation, overlooking their interdependencies and feedback mechanisms, thereby constraining coherent, cross-sectoral planning and sustainable resource management.

In response, the present research applies a Resource Nexus perspective to investigate the interlinkages among urban sprawl, landscape fragmentation, and habitat network connectivity. This approach emphasizes a system-based view for the integrated management of environmental resources and the interconnections to promote sustainable development.

Through a systematic review of geospatial modeling approaches, the study identifies and evaluates suitable analytical frameworks for assessing the spatial and temporal dynamics of these processes. The selected approach will then be applied to assess urban sprawl, landscape fragmentation, and habitat network connectivity in Sierra Leone. A model will be established for integrated assessment through a Resource Nexus perspective, enabling a comprehensive understanding of their interconnected effects.

The study will develop a comprehensive modeling framework that links spatial patterns to resource-use outcomes, providing a scientific basis for sustainable land-use and environmental policy. The findings will provide an integrated scientific basis for policy and planning interventions that balance urban growth with environmental resource sustainability, offering critical insights for applying the Resource Nexus approach in rapidly urbanizing regions.

Keywords: Urban sprawl, Landscape fragmentation, Habitat Connectivity, Resource Nexus, environmental resources

Contact:

Sesay, Sampha

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development
Germany

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TUD, Dresden University of Technology

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Museum für Naturkunde, Berlin

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Leibniz-Institut für ökologische Raumentwicklung e. V.

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Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL

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